

Online Conferences: International Conference on Green and Digital Economy

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Communicative Activity as a Paradigm of Educational Achievements

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Abstract. *Speech directly affects not only the intellectual development of students, but also the formation of their character, emotions and personality. This article discusses the role of speech in the communicative activity of 1st year students.*

Keywords: *student, speech, communicative activity, socialization.*

Introduction

A growing personality gradually acquires social experience, assimilates it, goes through the process of socialization and acquires more and more independence - the processes of individualization. Having reached a certain level, it gives rise to the self-government of a person who consciously organizes his life and thereby determines his own development.

The Russian scientist I. A. Sikorsky describes the period of early youth as follows: "... considers himself a "man" and calls himself "I". Self-consciousness of a person, that is, his "I", is based on the mind, emotion, will and spirit. All these parts come together to form the human personality. The process of development of the natural qualities of a person mainly occurs at the age of 15 to 18 years [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

Materials, Methods and Discussion

Self-aware students form their own "I". First of all, this happens by addressing certain groups of people. The growing schoolchild in the process of activity receives certain information about himself as a subject of activity and, on the basis of this information, establishes relationships with others. Communication with others begins to be not only a way of life, but also a source of information, most importantly, a way of self-expression and, to a large extent, a way of self-knowledge.

In the studies of U.A. Butaeva, it has been scientifically proven that if a person develops the skills of "understanding the feelings, thoughts and intentions of the interlocutor" in order to achieve success in the activities of early childhood, he will not encounter problems in "interpersonal communication". impact analysis" [3].

For 1st year students, the intensity and attractiveness of communication depend on the content of life. Finally, a characteristic feature of this type of communication in adolescence is the expansion of the space of personalized communication.

As the student develops his own self-concept, his personal position becomes the center of attention. They connect their thoughts with the universal knowledge that the education system provides [39].

So, it turned out that higher education is not a separate social institution, but an element of social relations with a mechanism of its own development and functioning. On our part, this position confirms the correctness of the principles of social adaptation and existential development, which have social significance in the process of innovative development of students' communicative competence [38]. Therefore, it is an important period for the formation of the social maturity of first-year students.

L. S. Vygotsky states that a person is social by nature and "therefore, the socialization of external and internal speech is of decisive importance in the development of children's thinking." In his opinion, "speech is a central function of social communication and cultural behavior of a person" [4].

The speech activity and development of the growing adolescent is his social thinking, speech regulation of the behavior of another person through words, which gradually leads to the development of his own behavior. Thinking is the highest level of introspection and involuntary behavior [14, 15, 16, 35].

According to the scientist, thinking means "attracting the mind." In adolescence, thinking, like language, develops "mainly under the influence of social factors" [4, 36, 37].

In our opinion, language activity is the basis of the discursive side of social relations, and language itself is the most common means of communicative relations in the human environment. Language in itself is not knowledge, but a means of communication, acquisition, thinking, creation of new knowledge, its storage, development and transmission [17, 18, 19].

Speech directly affects not only the intellectual development of students, but also the formation of their character, emotions and personality [20, 21, 22, 23].

Language is a useful tool in solving any psychological problem. Not exactly an assistant, that is, a leader. Although linguists evaluate language as a "tool of thought", "helper memory", "internal technique", "means of technical support", "spiritual technique", "intellectual tool", it is not capable of solving a single problem and only a person as a product of work of the brain through consciousness, together with language work, manifests itself in the "general adaptive system of a person" [24, 25].

Such an understanding of the problem requires consideration of communicative competence at the level of the content of education on its scientific and practical grounds [26, 33, 34].

The presented concept corresponds to our research idea of the mutual balance of two principles - emotional-developing and social-adaptive in the process of effective development of students' communicative competence. The emotional level of the process of formation of communicative competence analyzed by us is combined with the personal development of students. As a result of this approach, the language has a pedagogically complete constructive value [27, 28, 29].

Conclusion

The leading place among the freshman is occupied by such motives as preparation for an independent life, self-awareness, and the motive based on achieving one's goals comes to the fore. They are well aware of their attitude to learning and their motivation for learning. The student begins to actively study the socio-cultural space, "creates" and develops himself in social activities, which leads to the real disclosure of his "I" [30, 31, 32].

At the same time, a developing person begins to consider himself not only as an object of study, but already as an object of study.

As a result of socio-political and economic life events, a student, surrounded by knowledge and a large amount of information, finds himself in a space where personal "text-creation" becomes a way of self-realization. As a result of creating the text, the student is able to "realize his own "I" as an independent person, his positive qualities and negative qualities, be able to distinguish bad from good, right from wrong, cultivate the qualities of spiritual perfection in himself and form as a person, independent thinking and product thoughts correctly, helps to speak correctly and fluently" [5].

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НЕЗАВИСИМОГО РЕГУЛЯТОРА РЫНКА ЦЕННЫХ БУМАГ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the legal status of the securities market regulator and the relationship of this body with minority shareholders whose rights and legitimate interests have been violated. The article also analyzes the emerging conflict of interests in the protection of shareholders' rights.*

Key words: *Securities market, regulator, control, protection of rights, minority shareholders, joint-stock company, IPO.*

Аннотация: *Данная статья анализирует правовой статус регулятора рынка ценных бумаг и взаимоотношения этого органа с миноритарными акционерами, чьи права и законные интересы нарушены. Также статья анализирует возникающий конфликт интересов при осуществлении защиты прав акционеров.*

Ключевые слова: *Рынок ценных бумаг, регулятор, контроль, защита прав, миноритарные акционеры, акционерное общество, IPO.*

История регулятора рынка ценных бумаг в Республике Узбекистан весьма интересна, так как за все свои 30-лет существования статус регулятора переходил от одного органа к другому несколько раз.

После обретения независимости, в Узбекистане начал формироваться рынок ценных бумаг и контроль над функционированием данного рынка был возложен на Государственную комиссию по ценным бумагам и биржам, который был при Министерстве финансов РУз.

По Указу Президента РУз от 26.03.1996 г. № УП-1414¹ на базе Государственной комиссии по ценным бумагам и биржам, был образован Центр по координации и регулирования рынка ценных бумаг, которому были и переданы полномочия вышеназванной комиссии по регулирования рынка ценных бумаг Республики Узбекистан. Стоит отметить, что данный центр не был независимым и функционировал при Комитете по управлению государственным имуществом и приватизации Республики Узбекистан.

Однако, данный орган осуществлял свою деятельность до 2019 года, так как Госкомимущество было упразднено и, соответственно, нижестоящая организация в виде Центра по координации и регулированию рынка ценных бумаг была также упразднена. На базе ликвидированного Центра было создано Агентство по развитию рынка капитала в соответствии с Постановлением Президента Республики Узбекистан, от 24.01.2019 г. № ПП-4127.

Несмотря на то, что Агентство намеревалось стать не зависящим ни от чего и ни от кого на рынке ценных бумаг, данная организация также через два года существования была упразднена. Полномочия по регулированию рынка ценных бумаг были переданы Министерству финансов Республики Узбекистан. Статус регулятор вернулся на круги своя и как это было в начале 90-хх прошлого века начал принадлежать Министерству финансов.

По опыту всех стран, модель регулирования рынка ценных бумаг можно поделить на три вида: 1. Регулятором выступает независимая организация, например, как SEC (Securities and exchange commission) USA; 2. Регулятором выступает Министерство финансов страны; 3. Модель смешанного управления.

Из почти 30 стран с развитыми финансовыми рынками 59 % имеют самостоятельные ведомства или организации, примерно в 15 % странах за рынок отвечает министерство финансов, 15 % стран имеют смешанную модель управления. В странах с устойчивой банковской моделью рынка (например, Германия, Австрия и Бельгия) основная ответственность за рынок ценных бумаг лежит на центральном банке или органе финансового надзораⁱⁱ. Уникальной в этом отношении является Швейцария, где нет единого государственного органа, централизующего регулирование рынка ценных бумаг (эта функции разделены по регионам).

Как видно из вышеописанной краткой истории регулятора рынка ценных бумаг, модель регулирования данного рынка менялся в течение всего времени. И на сегодняшний день, в Узбекистане применяется 2-модель регулирования, то есть само Министерство финансов является уполномоченным органом.

Однако, данная практика, на наш взгляд является спорной, так как в данном случае регулятор должен быть независимым как в США и не должен входить в определенную структуру.

Почему независимость регулятора необходима в нашем случае? Главной причиной является одна из задач регулятора – защита прав и законных интересов.

При осуществлении данной задачи, можно наблюдать за конфликтом интересов.

Если изучить корпоративное управление Республики Узбекистан, а именно орган корпоративного управления акционерного общества – Наблюдательный совет, то можно заметить, что во многих таких органах национальных акционерных обществ присутствуют представители государственных органов. Часто такими членами наблюдательного совета выступают руководители соответствующих органов и организаций и в особенности Министерства финансов. Примером такой практики корпоративного управления могут послужить Акционерные общества «Алмалыкский ГМК», «Узнацбанк», «Алокабанк», «Микрокредитбанк» и тд.

Хотелось бы отметить, что именно вышеназванные акционерные общества по решению Президента Республики Узбекистанⁱⁱⁱ должны провести Первичные и Вторичные публичные предложения своих акций, то есть их акции должны уже продаваться неограниченной публике, что означает расширение круга акционеров данных акционерных обществ. Этот факт также означает, что количество миноритарных акционеров в данных обществах также увеличится.

Как осуществляется защита прав миноритарных акционеров?

В случае нарушения со стороны акционерного общества прав и законных интересов акционеров, данные лица могут обращаться в Министерство финансов РУз за защитой своих нарушенных прав^{iv}. В данном случае, возникает вопрос: в качестве кого Министерство в

данном случае должно выступать, регулятором или одним из членов наблюдательного совета. То есть в данном случае возникает конфликт интересов.

Что такое конфликт интересов и в данном случае какой конфликт интересов может возникнуть?

Как приводит в своем Руководстве по разрешению конфликтов интересов на государственной службе Организация экономического сотрудничества и развития (ОЭСР), "Конфликт интересов" - это конфликт между общественно-правовыми обязанностями и частными интересами государственного должностного лица, при котором его частные интересы (вытекающие из положения государственного должностного лица как частного лица) способны неправомерным образом повлиять на выполнение им официальных обязанностей или функций^v.

И именно возникновение конфликта интересов может затормозить процесс защиты прав и законных интересов миноритарных акционеров.

Возникновение такого рода конфликта может стать причиной пересмотра своего решения инвестировать со стороны потенциальных иностранных инвесторов и не приобретать акции национальных компаний. Следовательно, именно некая зависимость регулятора рынка ценных бумаг может затруднить эффективное осуществление IPO (Публичного первичного предложения) национальных компаний.

С призыва развития национального рынка ценных бумаг, необходимо отделить и сделать независимым орган, на который возлагаются полномочия по регулированию рынка ценных бумаг, в том числе и публичных ценных бумаг.

Стоит в данном случае также отметить, что Республика Узбекистан намерена стать членом Международной организации комиссии по ценным бумагам и внедрить принципы данной организации по регулированию рынка ценных бумаг^{vi}.

В нашем случае, данный документ в первую очередь устанавливает 8 принципов по организации деятельности регулятора рынка ценных бумаг, и далее уже по регулированию других вопросов рынка ценных бумаг.

Особого внимания среди этих принципов заслуживают принципы 2 и 8. А если быть точнее то:

Принцип 2. Регулятор должен осуществлять свою деятельность независимо и действовать самостоятельно при реализации своих функций и полномочий.

Принцип 8. Регулятор должен стремиться к обеспечению недопущения конфликтов интересов и неравного отношения на рынке, а также их устранению, раскрытию или регулированию.

Как раз таки вышеназванный случай с участием должностных лиц регулятора в деятельности акционерных обществ и противоречит этим названным двум принципам регулирования рынка ценных бумаг.

На основе вышеизложенного, мы можем предложить следующие два пути решения вопроса во избежание конфликта интересов:

1. Сделать независимым от Министерства финансов, самостоятельный орган, регулирующий рынок ценных бумаг;
2. Исключить должностных лиц Министерства финансов РУз из наблюдательных советов акционерных обществ, чьи акции продаются на бирже.

ⁱ Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан, от 26.03.1996 г. № УП-1414 «Об образовании центра по координации и контролю за функционированием рынка ценных бумаг при госкомимуществе Республики Узбекистан» Ведомости Олий Мажлиса Республики Узбекистан, 1996 г., № 3, ст. 30;

ⁱⁱ А.Рот, А.Захаров, Я.Миркин. Основы государственного регулирования финансового рынка. Зарубежный опыт. Учебное пособие для юридических и экономических вузов. М.: Юридический Дом 'Юстицинформ', 2002.- ст.

ⁱⁱⁱ Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан, от 13.04.2021 г. № УП-6207 «О мерах по дальнейшему развитию рынка капитала» НБДЗ: № 06/21/6207/0334 от 14.04.2021 г.

^{iv} Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан, от 13.04.2021 г. № ПП-5073 «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию системы регулирования рынка капитала» Национальная база данных законодательства, 14.04.2021 г., № 07/21/5073/0335

^v РУКОВОДСТВО ОЭСР ПО РАЗРЕШЕНИЮ КОНФЛИКТОВ ИНТЕРЕСОВ НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЕ <https://www.oecd.org/gov/ethics/49106105.pdf>

^{vi} «Цели и Принципы регулирования рынка ценных бумаг» <https://www.iosco.org/library/pubdocs/pdf/IOSCOPD561.pdf>

Implementation of Digital Regulation in Financial Sectors

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Introduction

The new global digital economy may trigger a real disruption in the financial sector, with new players, services and ways of doing business. The extent to which it will occur is still unknown, but there are reasons to think that we are at the beginning of the digital revolution in the financial sector.¹ To give just a few examples, in June 2019 the financial world was shocked by Facebook's announcement to create a cryptocurrency (Libra now called Diem). It is worth noting that a chat application as popular as WhatsApp (Facebook) is already providing payment services in some parts of the world, enabling users to make transactions to their contact list. It is also very significant that in the US some states have approved legislation allowing cryptocurrency companies to obtain a bank license, subject to specific conditions.² We have also just witnessed the first major cryptocurrency exchange to go public in the US (Coinbase). The mayor of Miami has even proposed to pay municipal workers in Bitcoin, in efforts to make the city a centre for tech industry innovation.

We can assume that this overall process is very likely to bring clear benefits in terms of competition, innovation and efficiency. However, at the same time, we cannot overlook the serious risks that the global digital economy involves for the financial system. On the one hand, the digital economy could lead to a very concentrated financial market, dominated by a handful of big techs, which could replace commercial banks in the provision of financial services ("And yet a world without banks is also visible on the horizon").³

On the other hand, decentralised finance (DeFi) is a quickly rising phenomenon seeking to eliminate intermediaries in financial transactions, which would be replaced with software protocols.⁴ In both scenarios, financial regulation and supervision would become extremely difficult. Monetary policy could also blow away from state control and even financial sovereignty would be under threat.

Personal data protection

New technologies are rapidly transforming the financial sector. In some countries robots are already performing banking tasks, such as customer contact and processing of loan applications.¹⁰ The importance of big data, machine learning and AI in the financial sector is expected to grow.¹¹ All this can lead to a more efficient financial sector, but it also raises a number of questions. Among

¹ Wuermeling, J. (2021) Combining stability and innovation—the Bundesbank and fintech players in the digital financial ecosystem. BIS [<https://www.bis.org/review/r210129a.htm> (accessed 29 January 2021)].

² Emamian, M. (2021) The Cowboy State Tames Bitcoin's Regulatory Wild West. *The Regulatory Review*, 7 April [<https://www.theregreview.org/2021/04/07/emamian-cowboy-state-tames-bitcoins-regulatory-wild-west/> (accessed 7 April 2021)].

³ *The Economist* (2021) A future with fewer banks, 8 May [<https://www.economist.com/special-report/2021/05/08/a-future-with-fewer-banks> (accessed 6 May 2021)].

⁴ Massari, J. and Catalini, C., "DeFi (2021) Disintermediation, and the Regulatory Path Ahead. *The Regulatory Review*, 10 May [<https://www.theregreview.org/2021/05/10/massari-catalini-defi-disintermediation-regulatory-path-ahead/> (accessed 10 May 2021)].

them, the protection of personal data is a matter of serious concern. The financial sector is a big source of data, which can easily be collected and treated by operators. We cannot exclude that the interest of large technology companies in providing payment services, at least in part, is data collection. There is no equal sensitivity and degree of protection in relation to personal data in the different parts of the world. Significantly, there are important differences between the EU and the US in this respect. Nevertheless, the stricter EU legislation has exercised a wide influence in the world. To some extent, the EU's General Data Protection Regulation¹² has become the global standard.¹³ In the EU, there are limits to the processing of personal data resulting from the right of data protection, which is a fundamental right recognised at national level and by Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and by Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. In short, data are to be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and processed in a transparent manner. The point is that although having these guarantees the European legislation is very much based on consent given to the processing of personal data.¹⁴ In this regard, we should wonder whether this is actually sufficient to effectively protect personal data. Personal data may be the price for receiving services free of charge. However, every day we are giving our consent to the processing of our data without having had time to read on what we have agreed to. At least, we should improve the citizen's ability to make more informed decisions.¹⁵ Moreover, we could go a step further. It might be appropriate that legislation would prohibit more strictly the processing of personal data, as currently happens with medical data. Arguably, a rule could be established that payment intermediaries and commercial banks would not have access to the data, which would be encrypted. Access would only be granted to resolve disputed charges.

Conclusions

First, in a global digital economy, where citizens are increasingly dependent on services provided by big techs, consent-based protection of personal data might not be an effective way to protect the fundamental rights at stake. In this respect, it might be appropriate for legislation to provide more safeguards for the processing and transfer of personal data.

Second, financial business is expected to rely increasingly on big data and AI. The question is to what extent commercial decisions can be based on gender, age, tastes or consumption patterns. Commercial banks are private companies that seek to make a profit. In doing so, they also contribute to preserving financial stability and to the public good. However, some limits to the use of personal data may derive from the fundamental rights at stake. Where appropriate, it would be a task for legislators to set limits on the commercial freedom of financial actors, who would otherwise be able to make their decisions as they see fit. Third, central banks and supervisory authorities are increasingly using new technologies to exercise their regulatory and supervisory competences. However, the mere use of new technological tools -including machine learning and AI- do not seem to alter the legal foundations of financial supervision.

Fourth, it might be appropriate to pass a specific regulation for big techs holding a gatekeepers' position to ensure financial stability, a level playing field between operators and consumer protection. In fact, the proposed Digital Markets Directive, if adopted, would apply to financial services provided by big techs.

Fifth, a specific regulation for crypto-currencies seems necessary to protect consumers and eventually the financial stability. This is why some countries have passed some it at EU level.

Sixth, the creation of an official digital currency might be necessary for sovereign money to continue to fulfil its role in a digital world. However, it should carefully consider its multiple implications in order to avoid its potential drawbacks. In particular, it should seek to minimise its impact on the financial system to ensure that commercial banks and payment service providers continue to play a strong role in the economy.

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A New Approach to the Concept of Credit and Monetary Policy in the Uzbek Banking Sector

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Abstract: *Their use creates significant opportunities for the growth of entrepreneurship across many industries, including the banking industry, in the context of the economy's digitalization. Under these circumstances, it is especially crucial to implement new technologies in monetary policy. This article describes the process for issuing loans, how digitization has improved them, and strategies for lowering risks when issuing loans. In these circumstances, a novel strategy is suggested for the relationship between the lender and the borrower, requiring the involvement of a third party in the evaluation of the business plan in order to obtain credit funds.*

A methodology for creating a business plan, operations for sustaining a business plan, and procedures for tracking the return of credit resources are all part of a novel idea for the banking sector.

The new idea means that the bank for the duration of the loan becomes a partner of the borrower in terms of the funds issued as credit. The borrower makes use of another person's financial resources to boost production quality or volume with the ultimate aim of improving production efficiency.

Due to the fact that credit resources are a tool for enrichment, the creditor whose funds are directly utilized in this process cannot be accepted as a partner, at least during the initial development stage. The author contends that the production development process cannot be abandoned in the absence of additional financial resources, and that the owners of those resources must be involved as partners during their development. After all, the owners of funds are just as risky with them as anyone else, if not more so. As a result, they are able to assert full ownership of property rights along with a stake in the manufacturing process.

Many times, after receiving outside funding, borrowers reluctantly return their debt to creditors, creating a number of risks. Risk-taking is not something that those who create it do; rather, it is something that those who contribute their resources do in order to recover their own do.

Raising the issue of when an investor turns into a co-owner will lessen risks in and of themselves. As long as they are complicit, lenders may legitimately assert that they should receive a portion of the profits made by the economy in question based on annual results.

Borrowers will try to settle accounts with the creditor as soon as possible and take care of unnecessary problems in order to ensure that there are no applicants for receiving funds from the distribution of profits for a longer period of time than the credit period. Risks as a concept in lending will be eliminated.

The fact that the creditors themselves will be able to obtain information on the intended use of the allotted financial (credit) funds, both from the borrowers themselves and from the tax authorities, is another circumstance that is not unimportant.

As a result, the monetary policy in the banking industry is drastically changing. With the issuance of loans, risks will be decreased, and banks' financial and credit resources will be used more frequently, which will have an impact on the revenue portion of the results of their banking activities.

The author suggests a novel method for calculating the business plan, which is based on the fact that the business plan was created in the bank itself, in order to further the idea presented. In reality, the borrower, at his own discretion, submits documents with business fee calculations. The business plan in this instance is biased toward the borrower's policy. The interests of the bank are not considered in this business plan.

A different approach to creating a business plan, which unbiased safeguards the interests of both parties of the four main subjects—the borrower, the lender, the bank, and the subjects of the economy—is required.

This kind of business plan will be computed by the IT system. Data entry from the borrower will serve as the initial source of information. The program will determine the amount needed to issue a loan, the length of the loan, and the borrower's exit based on the amount of profit realized from the launch of a business.

According to the preliminary calculations, it is possible to demonstrate on the graph that when the design capacity is reached, the maximum profit is obtained.

Additionally, small businesses and entrepreneurs for start-ups, who can be technoparks at regional district khokimiyats, can use the method for calculating a business plan widely. We believe that this will present a chance to draw interested investors, including both individual investors and agents for financial funds and investment banks, or financial angels.

The following are the results of implementing a business project development system:

- development of a standardized method for determining the "business plan" for the system of targeted financing (getting an investor);
- the investor's operational work with each client separately on a project;
- become a co-owner of a production unit during the time that a startup or business project is being financed;
- as a co-owner of financing, regularly receive operational information on the project from the enterprises and the STI bodies;
- for a specific amount of work completed, it is possible to determine the precise outcome of a startup or business project and the limits of its effectiveness (zero point);
- improving the level of project evaluation overall as a result of the adoption of a standardized methodology and the potential for operational control over investment projects;
- the availability of a digital financing plan for each project, which opens up the possibility of maneuvering to redistribute financial resources;
- the development of a system for tracking the progress of a financing project, which increases the level of return on the financial resources that are drawn in, speeds up the turnover of those resources, and lowers financial risks.

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Аннотация: Турли қияликка эга аркалар учун ванталар сабабли букланувчи моментларнинг энг катта қийматларини камайтириш.

Шарнирсиз аркада ҳаракатланувчи (ёки доимий бир томонламали) юкламадан эгилувчи ҳисоб-китоб моментларини камайтириш учун, арканинг таянч нуқтасини пролетнинг чорагида жойлашган нуқта билан бирлаштирувчи вантани (1-Расм) қўйиш мақсадга мувофиқдир. Ванта мавжудлигида, распорнинг рационал тақсимланиши юз беради [1].

Бу мақолада ҳаракатланувчи ва доимий (бир томонламали) юкларда доимий кесимга эга параболик шарнирсиз аркаларда ички кучланишлар катталигига вантларнинг таъсирини ўрганиш натижалари келтирилган.

Арканинг ҳисоб-китобда қабул қилинмаган. Интеграллаш [2] ишда бажарилгани каби, Чебишев полиномларидан фойдаланиб сонли усулда амалга оширилган. Бунда $\frac{l}{f}=2$ бўлган аркалар учун, ярим айлана олтига тенг қисмга, $\frac{l}{f}=4$ ва $\frac{l}{f}=8$ бўлган аркалар учун, тўртга тенг қисмга бўлинган.

Арканинг асосий тизими 2-Расмда тасвирланган. Ортиқча номаълумлар таъсири линияси тенгламалари электрон машиналарда ҳисоблаш учун жуда қулай бўлган даражали полиномлар кўринишида олинган. Бу тенгламалар мақола ҳажми чегараланганлиги сабабли, бу ерда келтирилмаган.

Вантасиз аркалар учун ортиқча номаълумларнинг таъсири линиялари ординаталари 1-Жадвалда, турли каттиқликка эга вантли аркалар учун эса ($k=E_a I_a / E_b F_b t^2$ – вантанинг нисбий каттиқлиги) – 2 ва 3-Жадвалларда берилган.

Пролетнинг ўнг ярим томонини бир текис тақсимланган юклама q билан юклашда вантли ва вантсиз аркаларда ички кучланишларни таққослаймиз (1-Расмга қаранг). Вантли ва вантсиз аркалар учун букланувчи моментлар эпюралари кўрсатилган, уларда аркадаги энг катта букланувчи моментларни ванта камайтиришини кўриш мумкин.

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Турли қияликка эга аркалар учун ванталар сабабли букланувчи моментларнинг энг катта қийматларини камайтириш 4-Жадвалда келтирилган.

Ванта – доимий кесимли шарнирсиз аркаларда ҳисоб-китоб букланувчи моментларни камайтиришнинг энг самарали воситасидир. Масалан, нисбатан енгил вантада ($k=0,0005$) ҳисоб-китоб букланувчи момент $\frac{l}{f}=4$ да 48% га, $\frac{l}{f}=2$ да 57% га камаяди.

Жуда оғма аркалар учун, берилган кесимли вантада самара бир мунча камаяди. $\frac{l}{f}=8$ арка учун вантада бошланғич чўзилишни яратиш, ҳисоб-китоб букланувчи моментнинг янада камайишига олиб келади.

Бўйлама ва кўндаланг кучларнинг қурилган эпюралари бўйича (мақолада келтирилмаган) кўрсатилган кучланишларни таққослаймиз ва ванта ролини аниқлаймиз.

Вантали аркалар ҳисоб-китоб бўйлама кучланишлари ортади, кўндаланг кучланишлари эса, вантасиз арка билан молиштириганда, камаяди. 5-Жадвалда таққослаш натижалари келтирилган.

маълумки, вантали аркадаги бўйлама кучланишлари $k=0,0005$ да 11-16% га, $k=0,000125$ да эса 15-24% га ошади.

Икки шарнирли аркалар учун [2] бўйлама кучланишларнинг ортиши $k=0,0005$ да 25-33% га ва $k=0,000125$ да 26-39% га ошади. Демак, шарнирсиз аркада ванта икки шарнирли аркага нисбатан, бўйлама кучланишларни камроқ ортишига олиб келади (тахминан икк марта).

Шундай қилиб, вантали аркаларнинг комбинацияли тизимини яратиш – ҳисоб-китоб букилувчан моментлар кескин камайиши ҳисобига (2-2,5 марта), енгилроқ иншоотларни лойиҳалаш имконини беради (ҳаракатчан ёки бир томонлама юкламада). Агарда ванталар мавжудлигида, арка ўқининг лойиҳадан четга камроқ чиқишини ҳисобга олсак, у ҳолда букланувчи моментларнинг ҳақиқий камайиши аҳамиятлироқ бўлади.

Хулоса қилиб айтиш мумкинки, кўрсатилганидек, схема бўйича оғма вантали ва қўшимча вертикал осмали аркаларни ҳосил қилиш – бу ҳаракатчан ёки бир томонлама кучланиш ҳолатида, энг рационал тизим бўлади.

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The Importance of Vocal Science in Musical Theater Acting

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Abstract: *This article tells about the importance of vocal science in musical theater acting, opening of its voice possibilities in the formation of musical theater actor.*

Key words: *Theater, actor, vocal, singing, music, sheet music.*

Theater is one of the types of art that gives a person strong spiritual nourishment, has an ideological and aesthetic effect, and gives pleasure.

For several years, the Uzbek theater has been living, growing and developing according to the socio-aesthetic criteria. Great stage models are being created in our national theaters, great directors and actors are developing.

Stanslavisky's teaching is very important in the formation of a musical theater actor. If a singing actor is brought up on the basis of this teaching, then his achievements in the field of singing are considered to be achievements of acting skills; he lives naturally on the stage, nothing distracts him from the creative process, and his whole body is freed from excessive tension. For example, the technical exercises of the actor, the basic elements of acting skills, correct breathing, etc. The artificial separation of the roles of the actor and the singer will only cause harm. If a student is a bad singer, then he is a bad actor. If he is a bad actor, then he does not meet the requirements of singing. Because musical theater acting and vocal studies are closely related to each other. A singer-actor in a musical theater is a person who performs complex actions from all the conditions of dramaturgy. Sound, its colors and the melody of sentences cannot appear without any basis. Every note, every musical sentence was written by the composer with a certain purpose. Therefore, the character and artistic style of the performance should be determined through this purpose. If it clearly expresses its purpose, then this is the live behavior of a musical symbol under certain conditions. In musical theater, the task of opening the feelings of the human heart is assigned to the voice. The first and main tool that implements the composer's ideas is the voice. Singing is a natural process that occurs in a person's normal psycho-physical state. Music requires the singer to have a smooth sound and be heard in every part of the hall. It requires a lot of skill and experience from the actor. To achieve this, the actor must work on himself and practice vocal science.

Requirements for an actor when singing:

There are different ways to adjust the volume. One is for actors and the other is for singers, both have different functions. Many opera singers have turned to monologues at the risk of losing their voices. Thus, their voice is designed for singing. Theater schools often misinterpret the opera program. Because most of them are opera singers, and the exercises are often performed together with the piano. In addition to the conscious and healthy use of the voice apparatus, there are two ways to

increase its capabilities: A) An actor must learn to imagine his vocal abilities in an unnatural way, which consists of imitating natural meaning and mechanical noise. Falling water, hitting stones, chirping birds, roaring motor; At first, these sounds are used, and then they are combined into the text of the speech, a combination of specific sounds appears (short words). This does not mean lowering your voice to a register that is unusual for you, using stylistic direction. Artificially manage the register in appropriate situations, but certainly without hiding the artificiality. There is another way to imitate the voices of women, children, old people, etc. However, an actor should never methodically force himself to lower his natural register to achieve a "male voice." This attempt is very harmful and causes inflammatory processes in the throat and even nerve diseases in the throat. Using the Voice If an actor suffers from minor voice defects that cannot be corrected by torturing himself, he must find a solution to the problem in various ways in order to fulfill his role.

We know that poetry is the basis of any song. Poetry is divided into different genres. Among these genres, ghazals are the lifeblood of traditional singing, particularly of national status.

In the process of training the singer, the teacher uses various methods. In the first place is the development of all the qualities of singing with the control of the training of hearing and perfecting. It is necessary to develop an idea of the correct organization of singing sonority in the student. Education is always conducted on the basis of musical materials, exercises, singing and artistic works. A well-chosen musical source nurtures the sound. Exercise is the main means of learning. Their application should serve as a means of eliminating the shortcomings that appear in the student's voice and require correction. Voice training exercises are a useful resource for transitioning from practice to performance. The teacher is required to prepare an artistic pedagogical resource while maintaining great decency. Analyzing sources taking into account musical, vocal-technical and performance difficulties is a necessary quality of a teacher. Acquiring a wide range of musical pedagogical resources and being able to use them is one of the requirements for the success of pedagogical activity. Learning and singing method is very important for successful performance of the piece. The student should learn how to work on the works in order to quickly master a wide and varied repertoire. . Development of singing breathing as the basis of singing takes place in the process of working on the sound and is gradually and systematically brought up.

It should be harmonious, free, and contribute to the natural coordination of all systems involved in the production of sound. Only the organized, calm breathing associated with singing creates the conditions for a sound that "rests on". Such a sound sounds full and beautiful.

Breathing is done before making a sound, this phase of breathing can be controlled, which is very important for teaching. In the process of singing breathing, the lungs are filled with air and the vocal apparatus is prepared to produce sound. The singing breath is taken with a rather deep, half-yawning sensation without noise.

Singing is a form of musical art in which melody and words are organically combined. Others call it musical speech. The part of the vocal apparatus that produces speech sounds is the articulating (pronunciation) apparatus, the members of which are considered the organs of pronunciation. These are: tongue, oral cavity, soft and hard palate, lower jaw, throat, larynx. The work of these organs aimed at creating speech sounds is called articulation. Singing articulation is different from speech articulation. When singing, vowels should be round, long, timbre and loud. Consonants are broken and pronounced quickly. The coordination and intensity of the work of the articulatory apparatus determines the quality of sound pronunciation, the accuracy of words - diction.

Correct pronunciation in singing relies on the pronunciation norms of the literary language - orthoepia (Greek-correct speech). The orthography of singing is different from that of speaking, when singing consonants are moved to the next syllable so that the syllable is open. If a singer begins to prepare a song from classical literature, but does not have the necessary preparation, does not

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understand what he is saying, at least the superficial meaning of the ghazal, then the logic is broken. Because he mispronounces because he doesn't understand, he misleads others by adding to himself.

In short, it is of great importance for students to deepen their vocal and technical knowledge, that is, to work on mixed breathing, to learn precise intonation, articulation, movement styles, to learn the artistic aspects of the work perfectly, and to improve their singing skills. It will be appropriate if it is approached with a thorough study of its possibilities.

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RESTORATION OF THE ASTRAKHAN INDUSTRY IN THE BUKHARA REGION OVER THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Annatation. *Based on archival materials, the article highlights the history of the restoration of the astrakhan breeding industry in the Bukhara region, identifies the reasons for the decline in the breeds of astrakhan sheep, measures to restore pastures, and take measures to create joint ventures. The policy of the state aimed at creating modern forms of management in the form of clusters is disclosed.*

Keywords: *fur, sheep, wool, infrastructure, region, cluster, joint venture, pastures.*

Introduction.

In the history of the peoples of Central Asia, the development of astrakhan breeding is attributed to the early Middle Ages, but they began to talk about it only during the invasion of the Arabs. In the 10th century, the Arab traveler Al-Istakhri, in his writings, mentions coarse-wooled sheep with curled wool, and the Arab geographer Ibn-Khaukal writes about the trade in astrakhan skins in the Khorezm Khanate. A number of scholars believe that its local name "arabi" is associated with the transition of the Arabs. About the Bukhara karakul, mentioned in the 17th century, when transport relations with Russia and Iran began.

During the years of Soviet power, the main wealth of the Bukhara region, along with cotton, was also karakul breeding. By the Decree of the Council of People's Commissars of the Soviet Union and the subsequent decision of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Uzbek SSR, the Bukhara karakul plant was created in 1926 [1], but the plant's capacity was not able to process karakul supplied from all over the republic, but additional plants were not built. Unprocessed raw materials were exported outside the republic. On the eve of independence, the region had breeding plants and many collective farms in the Sverdlovsk, Gijduvan, Karakul, Ramitan, Peshkun districts bred karakul sheep. In 1985, 1900 thousand pieces of karakul skins were processed at the Karakul plant, which is 102.8% more than in 1984 [2]. During the years of Soviet power, karakul plant was supplied to the former republics of the USSR in small quantities and at very high prices.

Analysis and results.

In 1990, the association "Bukhoro-Karakul" was created and in its composition: 9 state farms, 2 state breeding plants, 1 breeding farm, where 290 thousand Karakul sheep were kept. A year later, the association already produced 170 thousand sheep, 2.4 tons of meat, 400 tons of wool [3]. By a decree of the Cabinet of Ministers under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1992, purchase

prices for astrakhan fur were set at an average of 600 rubles per 1 piece; wool - an average of 120 rubles per 1 kilogram [4]. In 1993, in order to develop the astrakhan industry with bringing the production of astrakhan to world standards, a joint Uzbek-Greek enterprise for processing astrakhan astrakhan furs “Bukhara-Omega-Furs” was established [5]. Decision three years later by Khokim of the region for No. 433 of February 21, the plant was transformed into an open joint-stock company. But in the conditions of the underdevelopment of the work of market infrastructures, limited opportunities for karakul-breeding state farms, she was engaged in the implementation of the smallest parameters for the delivery of finished products.

Despite the measures taken by the state to restructure, optimize shirkats and farms and create conditions for the development of animal husbandry, by 2004, the production of skins of the Karakul breed of sheep decreased from 1.4 million pieces in 1990 to 700 thousand pieces [6]. In 2007, OJSC "Bukhara-Karakul" by decision of the tender commission dated October 26, 2007 No. 1 was purchased by LLC "Tomf" of the city of Tyumen of the Russian Federation, and a joint venture was created [7]. Karakul is supplied mainly to twelve vertical republics [8]. The proceeds of the joint venture in 2008 amounted to 213.9 thousand soums, and the net profit was 407.3 thousand soums, but the enterprise was soon liquidated [9].

The main areas for the production of karakul wool in 2011 remained - Dzhandarsky district, producing up to 31885 pieces of karakul sheep, Gijduvansky up to 26099 pieces, Karakulsky up to 18965 pieces, Ramitansky up to 18617 pieces and Peshkunsky up to 18394 pieces of sheep [10].

In 2012, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) prepared a pilot project that included the tasks of integrated planning of land use management processes for two ecologically and socio-economically representative districts of Zaminsky in the Jizzakh region and Karakul in the Bukhara region. The project was designed for 2014-2018 with a funding volume of 2,513,600 US dollars, from the bottom of 2,313,600 US dollars of finance from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and 200,000 US dollars from UNDP. The project document considered the solution of a number of topical issues, including issues related to land degradation, desertification, natural disasters, including landslides and mudflows, deforestation, impoverishment of pastures, which directly affect the development of karakul breeding [11].

In the course of the studies carried out by the Republican Commission for Deepening Economic Reforms in Agriculture, a proposal was developed for the reorganization of karakul agricultural cooperatives (shirkats) into farms and limited liability companies. Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Samarkand and Surkhandarya regions were included in this program. In the Bukhara region, agricultural shirkats: "Alat", "named after Amir Temur", "Galaba", "Jongeldi", "Karakul", "Karaulbazar", "Kukcha" were transformed into limited liability companies [12].

In order to increase the breed of astrakhan sheep, export of astrakhan sheep in 2020, scientific and breeding experimental stations were created in Kashkadarya, Bukhara regions, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan [13].

By the Decree of the President “On measures for the further development of sericulture and karakul farming in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, in all regions of the republic with pastures, until July 1, 2021, it was instructed to create karakul breeding plants for breeding purebred small cattle. According to the target parameters approved by the decree, the Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Navoi regions

have increased indicators for the production of astrakhan. In the Bukhara region, on the allotted 2355 thousand hectares, the number of astrakhan sheep was fixed and brought to 1968 thousand units [14].

Conclusion.

Thus, during the restructuring of the agro-industrial sector in the first years of independence, measures were taken to increase the breed of astrakhan sheep, to revive the industry in the Bukhara region. In 11 districts of the region, the activities of existing ones were restored and new breeding farms were created. An analysis of the creation and functioning of economic enterprises showed the existence of problems for the region associated with swampiness, salinity of arable land, lack of fodder for the development of animal husbandry, financial resources for doing business, etc.

In October 2020, a commission was established to conduct an inventory of the state of pastures intended for breeding karakul sheep in order to develop karakul breeding for the period from 2021 to 2025. The main components of the new innovative reforms were clusters in the karakul breeding industry, thereby solving the problems of increasing and expanding production of competitive goods based on deep processing raw materials

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Military History and the Origin and Development of the History of Military Art

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Annotation. *This article provides information about the history of military art and the origin of the first military operations, military uniforms and military tactics.*

Key words: *Military art, military uniforms, tactics and military styles, guns.*

The history of military art is one of those special disciplines into which the general history of culture is decomposed. Military institutions occupy such an important place in the structure of the state, wars, which open wide scope for viable states and remove decrepit organisms from the arena of history, constitute such an essential part of history that the history of military art has no less right to special study of it as a whole over the centuries than history of religions, constitutions, economic life, law. The division and specialization of labor in the study of departments of cultural history brings rich results. Investigating for thousands of years the relationship between the evolution of military art and the economic and political development of states, we immediately land on ground very rich in conclusions and generalizations.

Such is the position of the history of military art in relation to general science. Among the military sciences, the history of military art is the foundation on which other military disciplines are built. Without paying enough attention to military-historical study, it is possible to train only artisans of military affairs, who are not capable either of conscious creativity or of adapting and recognizing the rapid evolution of military affairs that is currently going through. In order to achieve positive results, military-historical study must by no means take on the character of military-historical illustrations that clearly explain the conclusions of an abstract theory, but must itself become the soil on which the strongholds of our military thinking are born.

The study of military history in Russia has been divided since 1865 into two disciplines: military history proper—the study of campaigns—and the study of the history of military art. According to the Minister of War Milyutin, who established this division [12], the history of military art should consist in a presentation of successive changes in the manner of warfare, from ancient times to the latest, and the main goal should be to indicate the influence that modern conditions had on the state of the art of war in every era. The history of military art, therefore, explores military phenomena not in their statics, but in their dynamics; its center of gravity lies in the study of the evolution of military art and the economic and political prerequisites that determine it.

Actually, military history, as we have established, studied the art of war in its statics. The study of the campaign was supposed to clarify the causal relationship between the action and the consequence that follows from it in strategy and tactics; the study of the campaign was preceded by a detailed study of the state of military art in the armies of both sides - strategy, tactics, administration.

We doubt the validity of this fundamental division. First, we do not even have to refer to the authority of the great Marxist Thinker, Franz Mehring, to establish the following position: in order to understand the manner of warfare of any people, it is necessary to study its political, economic and social condition. No one will argue against this truth now. Thus, the historian of war has just as little right to isolate himself from political and economic questions and wall himself up in purely operational problems, as does the historian of military art. Secondly, the study of each war becomes scientific and is of definite scientific interest only if this study is connected with the general course of the evolution of military art. And thirdly, the pace of evolution in our era has accelerated so much that during the same war we already observe the dynamics of evolution. Both the world and civil wars of recent years are very complex phenomena; military art stands at different levels at different moments, and we have no right to consider it statically, as something definite and immovable.

Therefore, every major work of military history will be, at the same time, a work on the history of military art. Military history, as a separate discipline, hardly has the right to exist along with the history of military art.

However, the study of the latter must, of course, consist not only in the passage of large steps through the arena of history, which is the task of this work and which is necessary in order to grasp the general character of evolution. This review of the evolution of the art of war itself became possible only on the basis of separate works, which carefully studied individual operations, devoting dozens of volumes to the questions touched upon here in a few lines. The history of military art, in addition to a general outline of evolution, should also consist in a detailed study of individual operations, as well as a detailed study of the development of important special departments.

The study of individual operations is necessary not only for the historian of military art, as data for the study of evolution, but also for wide circles of command personnel in order to give concrete content to their theoretical ideas on operational art and tactics. Criticism of the operational and tactical decisions taken by other commanders, in a situation absolutely precisely stipulated by reality, is the most scientific and perfect means of deepening our thought into the operational and tactical arts; however, in order to give a non-amateurish, frivolous criticism of the decision taken by the responsible commander, one must accurately study the situation in which the given commander was located, one must place oneself within the framework of exclusively those information about the enemy and his troops that he had. The study of operations thus organized, guided by common sense, free from any dogmatism, teaches one to quickly grasp and evaluate the situation broadly and deeply, makes it possible to foresee what consequences this or that event will cause, and it is easier to find the right decision. A commander who has delved sufficiently into the study of operations will be able to correctly and clearly formulate the vital questions that the situation poses to him, develop his eye, learn to beware of risky generalizations, and learn the concrete side of historical facts.

It is especially useful to study the history of operations that took place in conditions not too different from modern, i.e., later wars, and, if possible, in probable theaters of war, which will make it possible to assess what influence their statistical and geographical features had on the course of operations. Independent military-historical research is of enormous importance, since only an independent analysis of phenomena, and not memorizing someone else's, even the most brilliant criticism, will give the most fruitful results. A thorough study of even a small corner of the operation is much more valuable than a superficial acquaintance with many campaigns.

The achievements of the study of the general evolution of military art are much less utilitarian than the work on several operations. Acquaintance with the evolution of the art of war does not pretend to help in solving a specific operational or tactical task. And yet the history of military art is the basis of higher military education. It reveals to us, to the roots, the essence of all modern requirements of strategy, operational art, tactics, administration and, instead of slavery to dogma, gives us dominion over it. It shows, by establishing a causal relationship between the development of the state as a

whole and the evolution of military art, Under various conditions, the main military issues were resolved. It makes it possible to identify the causes of their current formulation, and prepares us to take into account the requirements that economic and political life imposes on military affairs. And the more vigorously the pace at which the development of the economic and political structure of societies proceeds, the more energetically the evolution of tactics and technology proceeds, the more important is the history of the evolution of military art.

No conscious creativity in military affairs is inconceivable without the development of a definite military worldview, without establishing the point of view from which the most varied phenomena will be judged. This broad military outlook is given only by comparing and contrasting different styles in military development, in tactics and strategy, by comparing and contrasting different eras.

Each specialty of military affairs has its own history. There are histories of military knowledge, infantry, cavalry, artillery, long-term fortification, sieges, supplies, military law, discipline, military technology, military organization, etc. Many of these special disciplines have their own very respectable, extensive and set on solid scientific ground. , literature. Along with such a division of labor according to specialties, special histories of military art for individual peoples tend to develop. Especially many works are devoted by the French to the study of the development of military art in France, and in Russia, since the 80s, the study of Russian military art has won a special academic chair for itself and has had such an outstanding researcher as Maslovsky.

In relation to these histories of special industries and national martial arts, it is necessary to take a firm stand. The general history of military art, first of all, should not be a mosaic of individual nationalities and specialties and should not turn into an encyclopedia of military historical knowledge. An attempt to cover [15] in one work all specialties and all peoples would lead not only to a huge swelling of its volume, but would be disastrous for its main idea, which would drown in a heap of colorful details. The history of military art sees a single process in the general evolution of the world, seeks to embrace it exclusively, and in order to characterize each epoch, it snatches from individual specialties, or individual peoples, individual facts that, from a national or special point of view, may not even be the most important, but most successfully outline world evolution National histories, histories of specialties are only colors on the palette of the general historian of military art. He has the right to pass over in silence very important specialties, to forget over the centuries about the state of military art among peoples who occupied a territory of hundreds of thousands of square kilometers - and is sometimes obliged to draw his attention to the details of the evolution of military art of some insignificant Swiss cantons lost in the mountains or to the army of the tiny Athenian Republic. Only he who speaks a new word, which will become the law of tomorrow for all, has the exclusive right to the attention of the historian of military art.

The emergence and development of the history of military art. The history of military art, like strategy, was born only towards the end of the 18th century, when human thinking turned out to be sufficiently prepared to move from anecdotal history to generalizing studies. Hoyer's first significant work, published in 1797, retains scientific significance to this day. Its center of gravity, in connection with the material nature of the philosophy of the eighteenth century, lies in the study of the evolution of military technology. The talented works of the emigrated Prussian officer Ryustov attracted the attention of wide scientific circles to the history of military art in the fifties and seventies of the last century. But in essence, only the achievements of historical science over the past forty years are laying a solid foundation for the history of military art. By the beginning of the 20th century, the history of military art was already a science recognized by civilian scientists, and in the person of Delbrück it won one of the leading departments of the history department of the University of Berlin.

The history of military art is now able to operate with immeasurably more accurate material than that contained in the works of previous generations, which accordingly increases its real significance. The requirements for accuracy of presentation and critical evaluation are now greatly increased.

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Modern methods of historical criticism are a powerful weapon to expose fables; court historiographers, which every sovereign of the 15th century strove to acquire and who enjoyed the greater respect, the more colorful their inventions were, are, it is true, even now, but already as a buffoon's ghost.

The introduction of the history of military art into the programs of all academies in the first half of the 19th century took place under the pressure of the authoritative demand of Napoleon I: "Wage an offensive war like Alexander, Hannibal, Caesar, Gustav-Adolf, Turenne, Prince Eugene and Friedrich; read and re-read their history 83 campaigns - and form your thinking on them; this is the only way to become a great commander and unravel the secrets of art; your consciousness, enlightened in this way, will reject the rules that are contrary to the principles that great people held.

By the beginning of the 20th century, the history of military art had certainly outgrown the Napoleonic program. The history of military art does not now seek to reveal a common unwritten code - the secret of the great generals - but puts before us the dialectic of history, in the light of which all the rules and principles of military art acquire a conditional and temporary character.

The study of the ancient world gives a complete, complete picture of the origin of militia armies, their transformation into professional armies, the flowering of the military art of Alexander the Great, Hannibal and Caesar, and in particular the latter relied on the highest economic achievements of the classical peoples. An understanding of the Roman legion and Scipio Africanus is highly desirable in order to be able to make a sound judgment about the militia system and the great problems of our time. The economic collapse of the ancient world led to subsistence farming and associated feudal forms of warfare. The knights have come to the fore, their art is a disease of individualism, each time arising on soil devoid of the economic and political prerequisites necessary for military affairs. Against the dark background of the Middle Ages, manifestations of Asian military art among the Arabs and Mongols stand out sharply, based on the highest achievements of technology, economics and politics, on the close adhesion of the broad masses with the tasks of war.

The transition to the new time in military art is marked by a high rise in the spirit of the masses, which allowed the Flemish and Hussite infantry to rally into units strong enough for a defensive battle, and the Swiss to create infantry armed exclusively with edged weapons and formed tactical units that developed an irresistible strike. Modern times—the 16th, 17th, and 18th centuries—developed this technique of cohesion into a tactical unit to a high degree. made up of the dregs of society, but so firmly cemented that on the battlefields they sometimes withstood up to 50% of losses. And the newest pages in history will begin with the great French revolution, which introduced a genuine people into the army and significantly improved the quality of the material to be consolidated in tactical units.

The road to this development was opened by the revival of the infantry in Switzerland. The infantry has been reborn in modern history in the form of militia in tiny states, just as in the ancient world we first get acquainted with the infantry in the form of militia of Rome and Athens, states with a territory of 40 miles across and with a population equal to Bern. This initial form of development of the infantry - the militia - turned out to be combat-ready, provided there were no too sharp contradictions between the interests of the urban and rural population.

The danger of the attack of the knights forced the revived infantry to form in deep battles - 50-100 ranks deep. As the cavalry danger was overcome, the infantry of modern history began to gradually move on to finer formations and, having received the cavalry itself to cover their flanks, stretched out into the wall of a linear battle formation.

Towards the end of the Middle Ages, whenever there is a glimmer of some kind of ray—in the form of taxes beginning to flow, the formation of reserves, the resurrection of money circulation, or a major social movement—every time we observe the emergence of healthy and vigorous shoots in the

art of war. The revival of capitalism in the 16th century directs the development military art in the mainstream of standing armies. The lessons of Maurice of Orange in the 17th century are assimilated throughout Europe; Louvois reforms the French army in accordance with them, and Peter the Great, forty years later, the Russian army. The ideas of Moritz, Louvois and Peter the Great are the ideas of the reformation transferred to the field of military art.

The line of military development of the 16th-18th centuries ran into a dead end in the military achievements of Frederick the Great. The Prussian army was a complex machine on a clay foundation that threatened to collapse every minute.

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History of Military Work in the Roman Empire

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history of the organization of military work in the Roman Empire, the achievements and shortcomings of the rise of military work.

Key words and phrases: Roman Empire, Roman Army, Slavery, Contubernia, Centuria, Manipula, Cohort, Allar, Vexilation.

After each state is formed, it must have its own powerful army to strengthen its territorial borders and protect its population. History is witness to the fact that statehood has been formed since ancient times, and that this process has been continuously developed and adapted to the times. This process had its place in the administration of Rome, one of the ancient developed states. Until today, the issue of military art, army, and military tactics of ancient times has attracted the attention of many researchers.

The 2nd century is the "golden age" of the Roman Empire. At this time, the empire had the largest territory. Its borders extended from Scotland in the north to the banks of the Nile in the south, from the Atlantic coast in the west to the Persian Gulf in the east. The slavery system reached the peak of its development. Many slave farms switched to producing goods for the market. Cruel oppression of slaves increased. During this period, the economy of the provinces and the life of the city here reached a higher level of development.

In the 1st and 2nd centuries AD, all the peoples of the Mediterranean region became part of the Roman Empire, a single huge state for the first time in history. The borders between individual states, which were turned into Roman provinces, were abolished. Rome achieved all this through its powerful army.

In almost all periods, only Roman legion had the following components:

Contubernia - 8-10 warriors; Until the time of Julius Caesar, the contubernia consisted of 10 warriors, and in later times - 8 warriors.

Centuria - 60-100 warriors. Centuria is made up of 10 contubernias.

Manipula - 120-200 fighters; Manipula consists of two centurias.

Cohort - consisted of about 960 fighters.

In addition, there are special auxiliary troops, which are divided into two groups: cohorts and allar.

In addition to these, there were also irregular troops, their exact and total number is not known, they were composed of barbarians.

The vexillations are special groups of troops separated from the legions. The vexillations were mainly part of the auxiliary force, they were sent as an auxiliary force to an army or to build bridges and other construction works. [1. C.130].

Military and political reforms were carried out at the initiative of Roman senate consul Gaius Marius. As a result of the reforms, a new well-trained army was formed. A large number of Teutonic tribes BC. In 102, Sextius was defeated by the Romans in a battle near Acqua. BC In 101 AD, the Cymru were defeated at the battle near Vertsella in northern Italy. 150-200 thousand Germans died in the battles. Many more were sold in Italian and Mediterranean slave markets. The main reason for such achievements of Gaius Marius was his military reforms. In the past, the Roman army consisted of volunteer units of citizens who were called up by necessity and returned to their peaceful activities after the end of hostilities. Serving in the army was one of the honorable obligations of citizens who had a certain amount of property and could provide themselves with weapons. The army formed in such a composition was perfect in the conditions of the Roman city-state. [3. B. 516].

The Roman army also had special military titles, which were distinguished by the following symbols:

The titles of officers:

1. Corolla (coronae);
2. Decorative spear (hastae purae);
3. Flags (vexilla).

Soldier titles:

1. Special necklaces (torques);
2. Special medallions (phalerae);
3. Special bracelets (armillae).

In addition to combat training, the maintenance of iron discipline ensured the high combat readiness and military potential of the Roman army for thousands of years. The following punishments were applied to those who did not follow the rules:

1. Barley bread was given instead of wheat bread;
2. Cash fine;
3. Temporary isolation or temporary camp temporary disarmament;
4. Touching the personality of discrimination in front of the legion;
5. Cruelty;
6. Delivery to the warriors for punishment;
7. Dismissal from office;
8. Shameful expulsion from the army;
9. In severe cases, the punishment was death

The death penalty was used for 3 types of discipline violations:

1. For refusal of military service;
2. In addition, for not performing the night prayer or for falling asleep while fasting;
3. For theft and false testimony, they were removed from the ranks and beaten to death with batons in front of the soldiers.

There is no doubt that the powerful army of ancient Rome was one of the main factors that made Rome so popular in the ancient world. Foot soldiers were considered the backbone of the Roman army. In addition, there was also a cavalry. But they did not form the basis of the Roman legion. Another strong point of the Roman army was the Roman navy, which was the master of the entire Mediterranean Sea for many centuries. The Roman navy enjoyed a clear superiority in naval warfare

throughout the Mediterranean basin for several hundred years, allowing for the movement of land forces in coastal areas and the delivery of troops to enemy territory by sea.

The commanders-in-chief had unlimited management powers over the army. All kinds of punishments are prescribed by them. Only those who do not have the right to sentence the officers to death are spared.

On the other hand, unwritten laws were also in place, for example during the Latin Wars in 340 BC, the consul Titus Manlius Norcavatus took his son Manlius out of the ranks for single combat, despite many pleas. executed [1. C.135]. This shows how much the Roman army paid attention to military tactics and that violating these tactics was considered a serious crime. As a light punishment, Octavian Augustus forced the warriors to stand in front of the palace for a day on one yacht.

The following conclusion was reached during the study of the research. According to the manuscripts of ancient authors and the monuments of Roman law, the information about the oldest kingdom of Rome dates back to the VIII-VII centuries BC. For a long time, the information related to this period was emphasized as unreliable and false information. However, as a result of the archaeological and linguistic data obtained in the last decade, it was concluded that these data are correct and can serve as the most important source of the emergence of ancient Roman history. In particular, the date of the foundation of Rome (middle of the 8th century BC) is given correctly, as well as the information about the historical kings. Except for the first king. Now the name of the legendary Ramul is an important symbol in the stage of development of Rome. Information about the reign belongs to Cicero. Cicero (in the first half of the 1st century BC) lived and created. Legions formed the basis of the military structure in ancient Rome in II-III AD. The Romans founded the most perfect military organization of their time. This military structure allowed them to rule over their neighbors for centuries. Information about the structure of the Roman army is given in a number of sources, including Justinian's laws. In the laws of Justinian, the manuscripts of Roman jurists on military law from the end of the II century to the beginning of the III century have been preserved. These documents discuss military crimes, legal titles of military personnel and their legal obligations. The authors of the document were not only lawyers and statesmen, but also specialists who implemented their ideas.

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The Actuality and Theoretical Basis of Market Mechanisms in Financing Investment Activities

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Abstract: Searching for a new model of economic growth, the transition to an innovative model of the country's development in the modern conditions, and the problems of developing its investment activity occupy one of the leading directions. In addition, they are an important factor in the formation of a competitive national economy. In such conditions, it is necessary to create all conditions for attracting local and foreign investments and financing based on the clear definition of the goals and priorities of investments, rational regulation of investment activities, and formation of the investment.

Key words: Market Mechanisms, Financing, Investment.

In accordance with the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan¹, the task of further improving the investment environment in the country and increasing its attractiveness, taking measures to attract 120 billion US dollars, including 70 billion dollars of foreign investments has been set in the next five years.

Many scientific works, books were written and definitions were given by foreign and domestic economists in the scientific-theoretical justification of the concepts of "investment activity", "investment activity financing" considered in our study. Also, there are different interpretations of the meaning of "investment", "investment activity" and "investment activity financing" in economic literature and scientific research. Having studied them profoundly, we have considered that it is necessary to pay special attention to the following definitions given to the content of investment activity.

We think, the important aspect of the definition of the concept of investment given by G.P. Podshivalenko and N.V. Kiseleva is that investment is the transformation of resources into investment, as an investment resource that is idle without being used is not considered an investment².

Professor of Economical sciences D.G. Gozibekov defined investment as a financial category as follows: "the content of investments consists of obtaining funds from clear and reliable sources, mobilizing them in a reasonable manner, maintaining capital value taking into account the level of risks, and obtaining the intended effect"³.

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by Decree № PF-60 of 28.01.2022

² N.V.Kiseleva, T.V.Borovikova, G.V.Zakharova, et al., edited by G.P.Podshivalenko and N.V.Kiseleva. Investment activity – 2nd edition, ster. – M. KNORUS, 2006. p. – 13

³ Gozibekov D.T. D. Investments in financing are notorious. T.: "Finance " publishing house, 2003. 26-rate

According to our point of view, the author explained the concept of investment in detail, in which special attention was paid to the source, intended use of funds, risk and efficiency, and investments were not considered separately as tangible and intangible assets.

We know that according to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities", investment activity is a set of actions of investment activity subjects related to the implementation of investments⁴.

As a result of the conducted research, we came to the conclusion that the essence of the concept of investment activity financing is not fully investigated.

Table 1 Scientific research on financing conducted by economists⁵

Authors	Scientific work conducted on Financing field
Y.A. Chernyavskaya	Special attention is paid to the innovative function of investment and is to develop the supply system for banks, insurance companies, lessors, to support innovative small companies and companies upgrading fixed assets.
D.A. Mesheryakov Y.A. Mesheryakov	Funding is a collection of forms, types, methods and means of covering enterprise expenses, as well as financial funds collected to ensure existing types of activities in the enterprise.
Kondratyeva M. N.	Financing is the financial resources of the enterprise are the financial income and receipts at the disposal of the economic entity, the fulfillment of financial obligations, the implementation of the costs of simple and extended reproduction and economic stimulation in the enterprises.
O.V. Malinovskaya, I.P. Skobeleva	Financing is a relationship of distribution, while the distribution of financial resources in an enterprise is a process of formation and use of monetary income and expenses.
Ryzberg B.A., Lozovsky L.Sh	Financing is the provision of necessary financial resources for the entire economy, regions, enterprises, entrepreneurs, citizens of the country, as well as various economic programs and economic activities.
Sh.I. Mustafakulov	Attracting investments in the financing of enterprises in the conditions of economic transformation is a system of giving and spending money and controlling their targeted and effective use.
U.A. Haydarov	Financing means spending money to purchase the elements necessary for the implementation of the investment project.
Definition of the author	Financing of investment activities is a process aimed at providing investment objects at market conditions at the expense of tangible and intangible assets of investors or attracted funds, including loans, bonds, shares, corporate and infrastructure bonds, investment shares and other securities.

In formulating the above definitions, we have focused on attracting investments based on market mechanisms.

In particular, the new mechanism for attracting investment in the reproduction of fixed capital should combine a set of investment financing sources, including state financial support for projects of social and economic importance, the main element of which is to determine the need for investment based on the current position.

⁴ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" Article 3

⁵ It was completed independently by the author as a result of the study of economic literature

Investment activities should be financed clearly and systematically, that is, in the form of an investment program. According to the modern results of the economy, the methods of financing investment activities in the economy of countries have not been studied in depth enough. Therefore, it is necessary to approach this aspect from the scientific side and to study, that is, to evaluate the sources of investment financing in the region in order to choose the right method.

An optimal solution to the problem of financing investment projects will be the formation of sources of investment resources for further development through the implementation of programmatic activities. In the process of collecting investment resources, it is necessary to direct them to long-term, strategic objects that allow to achieve significant changes in the situation in the region. The market mechanism of financing investment activity is a mechanism for attracting investment resources on the basis of market principles, independently or with the involvement of financial organizations, involving participation in shares or mechanisms involving debt relations, including the placement of securities.

Effective organization of investment activity, its development, attraction of investors, expansion of funding sources, legal regulation and improvement of this activity are considered to be the most important issues.

In order for the capital market to become the main market mechanism for financing investments, continuing to improve legislation in this area, including the integration of the local stock market into global stock markets, improving corporate governance, establishing the circulation of securities derivatives, increasing the types of securities, developing the bond market it is appropriate to accept the regulatory legal documents.

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The Ways of Improving Market Mechanisms of Financing Investment Activities in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: Nowadays a large-scale work is being carried out in the republic to increase the investment flow to our country, to improve the market mechanisms of financing investment activities, to improve the investment environment as a basis for encouraging the activities of investors, to strengthen competition between economic sectors and effectively regulate investment activities.

Key words: Market Mechanisms, Financing, Investment.

At this point, the existence of problems are waiting to be solved regarding the implementation of the current market mechanisms of investment financing and some mechanisms that are actively used in the advanced foreign experience, and it is necessary to improve the measures taken in this area.

On December 20, 2022, the head of state Sh. Mirziyoyev's addressed “Murojaatnoma” to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan and stated “...we will further improve the conditions for increasing local and foreign private investments in the economy. We have managed to increase the volume of investments from 30% of GPR in the last six years. Next year, about 30 billion dollars of investment will be attracted, of which 25 billion dollars will be private investments. In particular, we will launch more than 300 projects with a total value of 8 billion dollars, and 40 new large-scale projects will be launched”.

Ensuring the implementation of these tasks indicates that the improvement of the scientific and methodological foundations of investment financing is an urgent issue.

At the same time, it is necessary completely and effectively use the possibilities of privatization and public-private partnership in attracting active investments.

The growing demand for investments in foreign countries is due to the fact that many companies use different methods of attracting them. In particular, placement of shares of companies on the basis of IPO in the primary market is a way to increase their capital. This method provides the fairest assessment of the market value of assets.

Listed companies will be required to meet high standards of financial and business disclosure, as well as create investment appeal for potential investors.

An important factor for investors is the high liquidity of the company's shares and their profit due to the increase in their value. Over time, business owners can sell a portion of their stock portfolio on the open market or use it as collateral for a loan. Granting company stock options can lead to long-term incentives for key employees. By placing the shares of the company on the rightly selected stock market, the company is more widely known in the market, and the trademarks are established.

2023, FRANCE

Companies can raise huge amounts of money if they attract investors by placing their shares on the stock market through an IPO. In particular, as a result of the organization of the IPO practice, the US General Motors company increased its capital by 23 billion, Rural Economy Bank of China achieved an increase 22 billion US dollars.

As a result of the conducted research, we also carefully studied the companies that were among the top ten in the history of the stock market in terms of investment attraction, and that attracted a large amount of capital as a result of the initial public offering of shares. In 2019, the most successful public placement in the world was carried out by Saudi Aramco, the state oil company of Saudi Arabia.

Table 1 The 10 largest IPO transactions in the history of the stock market

№	Name of the company	Amount of invested capital (US dollar)	Activity field
1	Saudi Aramco (Saudi Arabia)	25.6 billion	Oil company
2	Alibaba (China)	25 billion	Internet sales
3	Visa (USA)	17,9 billion	Payment system
4	Enel S.p.A (Italy)	16,5 billion	Electric energy
5	Facebook (USA)	16 billion	Information technologies
6	Generalmotors (USA)	15,8 billion	Automobile industry
7	Deutsche Telekom (Germany)	13 billion	Telecommunications
8	AT&T Wireless (USA)	10,6 billion	Telecommunications
9	Kraft Foods (USA)	8,7 billion	Food industry
10	Uber (USA)	8,1 billion	Plarform

If we analyze the data of the table, the company "Alibaba group" was the company that successfully conducted the largest IPO operation in the history of the stock market since 2014 (Alibaba group - for 25.0 billion US dollars). In 2019, this result changed, because the largest IPO in history (Saudi Aramco - 25.6 billion US dollars) was successfully conducted by the company "Saudi Aramco".

We should emphasize that underwriters play a very important role in the successful organization of IPO and SPO operations. The Saudi Aramco company also attracted large institutional investors (banks, investment banks, investment companies, credit organizations and others) as underwriters. We can observe that institutional investors are acting as lead managers, financial advisors and international coordinators in the world's largest IPO operation. This, in turn, shows that institutional investors play an important role in IPO practices.

The IPO conducted by the Saudi Aramco company included several aspects. In particular, it is designed to attract capital with higher returns than other investments, including additional investments that better meet the needs of the cocktail market or diversify Saudi Arabia's sources of income.

In 2023, the President decided to implement a large privatization program, including the sale of about 1,000 enterprises.

At the same time, in 2023, the shares of our 10 largest companies and commercial banks will be publicly and transparently traded for our citizens based on the IPO mechanism.

In conclusion, the implemented privatization will serve to attract foreign investors to our country, reduce the state participation in the economy, develop the capital market and put the idle funds of the population into circulation.

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The Role of Assessment in the Educational Process Assessment Tasks Evaluation Methodology

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Abstract: This article discusses the modern assessment procedures for educational standards of professional education and the perspectives of educational quality control. In addition, a number of features of ability assessment are analyzed.

Key words: educational process, assessment content, assessment forms, subject, professional education, assessment characteristics.

Evaluation is the main element of any activity, because it allows to control the results, to determine the limits of the norm and to make decisions aimed at eliminating the causes of failure. Comparison of the current state of the object (process, state, system) with the benchmark based on the evaluation procedures.

Assessment in the educational process consists of collecting and analyzing information about the knowledge, skills, and competencies of the students.

Assessment is carried out for different purposes and can perform different functions.

Evaluation objectives are generally divided into two types:

- assessment necessary to make decisions on support for specific students;
- assessment used to form management decisions at various levels of the education system, from a specific educational organization to the Ministry of Education of the country.

In the first case, the results of the assessment affect the adaptation of the educational process (they are used to diagnose problems in the education of specific students and determine measures to eliminate them, as well as to plan individual educational trajectories) and are used to determine the level of mastery of the educational process. program by students. In the second case, he is talking about decisions to be made regarding educational institutions and their systems.

Various functions of evaluation in modern educational practice are known in establishing the educational achievements of learners: identification, diagnosis, motivation, education.

The determining function is performed by the final grades. They are used to record specific student achievements at the end of a curriculum or part of it. However, assessment can and should perform a diagnostic function for both student and teacher. By seeing exactly what is "not mastered", what is "mastered", what is "well mastered", etc., both the teacher and the student understand what needs to be worked on and what can be given less attention. In this case, the assessment serves as a tool for feedback and is called formative assessment. In addition to diagnostic, motivational and educational functions, formative assessment performs.

In pedagogy, the distinction between the concepts of "control of educational results" and "evaluation of educational results" is related to the distinction between the formative and specific functions of evaluating the results of learning educational programs.

Results monitoring is impersonal in nature. Its task is to determine the effectiveness of the implementation of the educational program. Evaluation of the results reflects the dynamics of learning the educational program for individual students, and the educational process is individual.

Depending on the goals, different evaluation approaches can be used: quantitative, criterion-oriented, comparison, expert, 3D-evaluation, self-evaluation.

A quantitative approach is used to assess the economic efficiency (or comparable aspects of social efficiency) of education. In this case, a set of quantitatively measured indicators and, if necessary, efficiency indicators are distinguished, by changing their values, the effectiveness of education is evaluated.

The criterion-oriented approach is based on comparing the obtained result with the expected, emphasized results using clear definitions. A simple example is educational standards that define a set of criteria describing the educational results of a particular student ("must know ...", "must have skills ...", " must have practical experience") The standard of education defines the level at which the necessary and sufficient level of convention (contract) is achieved for the possibility of continuing education at the next level and (or) starting a professional activity in society. It is this level that serves as the basis for a criterion-based approach to evaluating the educational outcomes of each graduate.

Benchmarking (standard method) at the first stage involves determining the best option of a product or service (the best textbook, educational course, colleges, universities, etc.). An important priority of this approach is that it establishes a specific visible benchmark for quality improvement.

The expert approach is used when the outcome being evaluated is immeasurable. The decision is based not on the direct results of calculations and experiments, but on the experience and intuition of experts. The learner understands the process of gathering evidence of activity and discussing it based on predetermined criteria with expert evaluation.

Currently, an expert approach is recommended to assess the level of formation of general competencies of students.

- the evaluation was developed in the model of the national championship of professions and business ideas. It includes three levels:
- personal self-assessment of the expressiveness of meta and special skills by the students of the championship;
- evaluation by customers of the attractiveness and quality of services offered and promoted by trainees, consumers
- professional and expert assessment of the quality of labor and special professional activities of trainees.

Self-assessment is an assessment of a person himself, his personal qualities, strengths and weaknesses, inclinations and abilities, knowledge and skills, skills and qualifications. Self-assessment as a pedagogical method in a certain sense opposes external assessment and complements it (for example, in the "3D-assessment" methodology).

At the heart of human self-evaluation is the mechanism of reflection. Reflex - allows him to make his thoughts, emotional state, their actions and relationships, usually the subject of all special review (analysis and evaluation, understanding and revision) and practical change (self-change, self-management) individual ability.

Self-assessment and reflexive skills are an integral part of any competence. The readiness of a person to determine his own destiny and ultimately the success of this self-determination depends on the

level of development of these skills. Self-esteem is one of the most important factors of independent, educated and responsible professional choice.

The use of self-assessment allows to ensure the participation of the student not only in obtaining the result, but also in its analysis.

Conditions for effective use of self-assessment in education:

- initial training of the learner in general principles and strategies for evaluating the activity and its results;
- the use of a certain list of criteria that allows more or less precise definition of a meaningful basis for self-evaluation. (for example, in the form of questions: "What did I succeed to the greatest extent and what - the least and why?" etc.);
- compatibility of self-assessment with external assessment (the latter can be given both by experts with competence and by other students, etc.);
- use of self-assessment results for independent planning of further actions. ("What should I do to prevent such mistakes in the future?", "What competences should be developed first to achieve the best result?" and others).

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Hududlarda Uy-Joy Kommunal Xizmat Ko'rsatish Tizimini Takomillashtirish (Toshkent Shahri Misolida)

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Kalit so'zlar: kommunal, uy-joy, tizim, biznes, tadqiqot, resurs, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, infratuzilma, samaradorlik, energiya.

Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi. Jahonning rivojlangan mamlakatlari tajribasidan ko'rindiki, har qanday mamlakatning taraqqiyoti undagi mavjud "inson resurslari"ning rivojlanish darajasi hamda ushbu omilning rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi zaruriy sharoitlar hamda rivojlanish uchun mos bo'lgan muhitning yaratilishiga bog'liq. Ko'rsatib o'tilgan sharoitlar hamda rivojlanish uchun mos bo'lgan muhit jamiyatning ijtimoiy rivojlanish darajasidan kelib chiqadi. Aholiga uy-joy kommunal xizmatlari ko'rsatish sohasining rivojlanish holati jamiyat a'zolarining eng muhim ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish asosida ularning mehnat qilish qobiliyatini tiklash bilan birga mamlakat iqtisodiyotida yalpi ichki mahsulotning sezilarli qismini yaratuvchi soha hisoblanganligi, shu bilan birga soha milliy iqtisodiyot energiya resurslarining sezilarli qismini iste'mol qilayotganligi tufayli jamiyat taraqqiyotining bugungi bosqichida ushbu sohani rivojlantirish dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Ushbu tadqiqotning obyekti Toshkent shahrining uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatuvchi tashkilotlari faoliyati hisoblanadi. *Tadqiqotning predmeti* esa hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirish (Toshkent shahri misolida) vujudga keladigan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy munosabatlar tashkil etadi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirishning samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Belgilangan maqsadni amalga oshirishni ta'minlash uchun quyidagi vazifalarni belgilab oldik:

- Toshkent shahri misolida(TSHM) uy-joy kommunal xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari;
- Toshkent shahridagi hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirishning boshqarish samaradorligi ko'rsatkichlarini baholash;
- hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari asoslab berish;
- hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini joriy etish bo'yicha ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.

Tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi quyidagilardan iborat:

- hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini rivojlantirish zaruriyati va bu orqali uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llarini asoslash;
- kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini rivojlantirishning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillardan samarali foydalanish yo'llarini aniqlash;
- zamonaviy uy-joy kommunal tizimini rivojlantirish orqali uy-joy fondining samaradorligini oshirish hamda 2026-yillarga istiqbol ko'rsatkichlarini ishlab chiqish.

Tadqiqotning asosiy masalalari va farazlari:

- tadqiqot jarayonida hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini boshqarish jarayoniga joriy etish usullarini aniqlash tadqiqotning asosiy masalasi hisoblanadi;
- tadqiqotning asosiy masalasidan kelib chiqqan holda hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini boshqarish jarayoniga joriy etilganda, boshqarish samaradorligi sezilarli oshishi va ko'zlangan maqsadga erishilishi faraz qilinadi.

Tadqiqotda qo'llanilgan metodikaning tavsifi:

- tadqiqot jarayonida iqtisodiy tahlil, tizimli va qiyosiy tahlil, boshqaruv qarorini qabul qilishga yondashuv, taqqoslash, tasniflash, analiz-sintez, induksiya va deduksiya hamda SWOT-tahlil usullaridan foydalaniladi;
- hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirish (Toshkent shahri misolida) jarayoni amaliyotga qo'llanilganda kelib chiqayotgan kamchiliklarni yoritib berishda tahlil usulidan foydalaniladi;
- uy-joy fondini boshqarishda o'rganilgan natijalar holati bo'yicha yondashuvlar orasidagi farq oldingi usul va berilgan ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar bo'yicha o'zaro taqqoslash usulidan foydalangan holatda amalga oshiriladi.

Tadqiqot natijalarining nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati. Tadqiqot ishining nazariy ahamiyati – mazkur masala yuzasidan kelajakda amalga oshiriladigan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarida shuningdek, “Kommunal infratuzilma va uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligini boshqarish”, “Uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti va boshqaruvi”, “Uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligida biznes-rejalashtirish” hamda “Uy-joy kommunal infratuzilmani tashkil etish va boshqarish” kabi fanlarni o'qitishda foydalanish mumkin. Tadqiqot ishining amaliy ahamiyati shundaki sifat menejmenti tizimini rivojlantirish asosida uy-joy fondini boshqarish jarayonida tashkilotlar ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot ishidan foydalanishlari mumkin.

Tadqiqot natijalarining nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati. Tadqiqot ishi kirish, uch bob va har bir bob uchun xulosa, umumiy xulosa, foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati hamda ilovalardan iborat bo'ladi. Ilmiy tadqiqot ishining kirish qismida mavzuning dolzarbligi, obyekti va predmeti, maqsadi va vazifalari, ilmiy yangiligi, masalalari va farazlari, tadqiqot natijalarining nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati, ish tuzilmasi tavsifi yoritib berildi.

Asosiy qism 3 bobdan tashkil topgan bo'lib:

- birinchi bobda hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy-uslubiy asoslari yoritiladi;
- ikkinchi bobda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini hududlar kesimi bo'yicha takomillashtirishning (Toshkent shahri misolida) tahlili amalga oshiriladi;
- uchinchi bobda hududlarda uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimini takomillashtirishning (Toshkent shahri misolida) samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari asoslab beriladi;
- uch bob bo'yicha yoritilgan ma'lumotlar yuzasidan xulosa qilinib ilmiy tadqiqot ishi doirasida ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.

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Market Economy and its Emergence

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the market economy and its emergence, the development of human society, the fact that the market economy is a universal human economy, the market economy has existed for many centuries, and it has risen to the level of universal value only at the current stage of development.*

Key words: *market economy, individual society, socio-economic, universal economy, economic relations, effective use of universal value, free, spontaneous development, abstraction.*

The development of human society has shown that the market economy is a universal economy. The market economy has existed for many centuries and has risen to the level of universal value only at the current stage of development. The market economy went through the following stages in its development. Initial, "bud", free, regulated, deformed market economy.

1. Initial, "bud" market economy. At this stage, the market economy is just starting to take shape. Market relations and connections happen randomly and happen in the form of exchanging one commodity for another commodity. But since then, the market has started to play a big role. The stratification of society members and the development of the production of one or another commodity began to be emphasized.

2. Free, spontaneously developing market economy. It consists of scattered, disjointed activities, in which the goals and actions of producers and consumers are not mutually agreed upon. Of course, there is a difference between the initial stage of the free-spontaneous market economy and the later classical stage. But, in general, the classic market economy is distinguished by a number of features:

1. The number of participants of market relations is not limited, there is free competition between them.
2. All members of the society can engage in any economic activity.
3. Availability of production factors at a high level of mobilization: there are no obstacles to the movement of capital.
4. The size of the opportunity to receive information about changes in the market.
5. Absolute similarity of one type of goods (no trademark).
6. There are no monopolies, the state does not interfere in the market and its activities.
7. Blindly producing goods for an unknown market, the uncertainty of their sale or not.
8. It, in turn, causes the economy to develop through difficulties, economic stress and crises, economic losses.
9. Dominance of single, individual private property, accumulation of property in the hands of a minority, as a result:

a) causes people to separate into super-rich and super-poor classes;

b) creates an environment for competitive rivalry.

In the conditions of a free, spontaneously developing market economy, it is determined in the market whether the quantity and quality of the produced goods meet the demand, the costs incurred are covered by the fixed price, and whether the profit is seen or not. With the development of the market economy, manufacturers are looking for ways to adapt to customer demand. But, in general, the free market is an abstraction. In reality, there is no complete freedom, nor can it be. Only on the basis of understanding economic achievements, knowledge of existing legal laws, it is possible to set up one's activity in the most profitable way. It is impossible to have complete economic freedom, but there is enough freedom to ensure economic development.

3. The economy achieved by human society as a result of long historical development is a civilized (regulated) market economy. In a regulated market economy, the state exerts its influence by setting measures to alleviate unexpected tensions. Of course, these measures should not limit the freedom of activity of business entities, creative work and initiative. A civilized market economy also has its own characteristics:

1. In addition to private property, there will be other forms of property.
 2. Production is carried out taking into account market demand. Marketing plays an important role. The uncertainty is reduced.
 3. Honest competition takes the main place, its cultural methods are used.
 4. Long-term permanent relations, mutually beneficial partnership relations will be established between economic subjects.
 5. Due to the state's involvement in economic life and participation in regulating the economy, deep economic crises do not occur. Even if they do, measures will be taken to quickly get out of it.
 6. When the economy reaches a high level, the society becomes rich, so entrepreneurs work not only to get rich, but also to gain prestige and respect.
 7. The economy will be socially oriented, aimed at helping the poor and ensuring public welfare.
 8. Economic stratification of people will be limited. In society, the self-sufficient population is the main layer. In the conditions of a civilized market economy, regulation is focused only on limiting the negative consequences of the market. From this it can be concluded that in the conditions of the market economy, the market, first of all, regulates itself, besides, the state also affects the regulation of the economy. Economic, organizational-administrative and, finally, socio-psychological methods are used in market management. Only, as the economist V. Leontiev showed, the most important thing is to find the optimal level of state regulation with self-management of the market. So far, there is no country that perfectly meets this requirement. Excessive state intervention in the regulation of the market economy leads to deformation of the market economy.
- 4.** Deformed market economy. A totalitarian, centrally planned system based on administrative command is the most vivid example of a deformed market economy. It has the following aspects:
1. Absence of market entities based on different forms of ownership.
 2. The distribution of resources is excessively centralized in commercial activities of independence.
 3. Dominance of monopolies in production.
 4. Violation of the balance of demand and supply, its increasing.

5. Absence of a national labor market .
6. Deformation of commodity- money relations , predominance of non-market relations.
7. It is characterized by a lack of desire to conduct effective economic activities, deformation of the economic interests of all subjects, etc.

As a result:

shortage of goods increases;

- a) consumers' choice becomes more and more limited;
- b) "secret economy", the speculation market will flourish more and more.

Only by ending the deformation of the market economy, it is possible to end its negative consequences only if normal conditions are created for the development of the market. There is a big difference between the primitive and civilized stages of the market economy . The market economy differs in its quality according to the level of maturity. The essence of the market economy is reflected in its main features . They are as follows:

1. The market economy is based on the diversity of ownership. The economic base and economic system of any society begins with ownership. Depending on being a property owner or not, each person's position in society, that is, social status, arises. On the basis of ensuring the equality of all forms of property, property monopoly (single ownership) is not allowed. Property forms develop without restriction. There are also different ways of conducting business, which are characteristic of the forms of property , and this, in turn, first of all, determines the type of activity according to the intelligence, insight and other qualities of each person given by nature.

allows free choice. The existence of different forms of ownership and their equality is the basis of economic pluralism. Secondly, the diversity of ownership creates the necessary environment for competition in society. Development of society cannot be achieved without them.

2. Market economy is a free economy. The basis of freedom of economic activity is the ownership of production factors and created goods, and the independence of property owners . Everyone can engage in any economic activity they want without violating existing laws . The basis for this is the legally guaranteed diversity and equal rights of ownership.

3. Market economy is an economy that rejects monopoly. Economic monopoly is the exclusive dominance of a corporation, firm, organization or state in the economy or in a field. The basis of monopoly is the exclusive dominance of a certain form of property in the economy. Monopoly by its very nature creates stagnation, limits initiative, etc. That is why the market economy cannot come up with a monopoly. It has an antimonopoly orientation .

4. Competition plays a key role in the market economy . Competition is the driving, regulating and controlling force of the market economy. Competitive struggle encourages to increase labor productivity, improve the quality of work, introduce new equipment, technology, and use economic resources efficiently. In order to compete, it is necessary to quickly adapt to changes in demand, to produce goods that meet the needs of the population . As a result, the competitive struggle leads to the forward development of the economy . This does not mean monopoly even if there is a monopoly. Because competition is regulated by the state. Antimonopoly forces will be established and equal opportunities will be created for all subjects of the market economy. How to use this opportunity depends on business . In the market economy, on the one hand, interests collide and compete, on the other hand, subjects strive to harmonize their activities, and therefore their interests. Because their business will not work if they only compete. These are two opposing sides in economics. Economic integration also encourages economic entities to align their interests and compromise. With increasing interdependence in production , it becomes difficult to get good profits

without integration. Increasing specialization of production increases the interdependence of firms and enterprises. As a result, commercial relations are constantly established between them, in which not giving advice to their partners plays an important role.

5. In the market economy, prices are formed freely, based on the ratio of supply and demand. The price is determined by negotiation between the seller and the buyer. If the seller intends to make a profit by covering his expenses, the buyer thinks that he will get the highest profit. Money is the main means of economic relations. Liberalized prices lead both seller and buyer to always operate on a cost-conscious, profit-and-loss basis.

6. In the conditions of the market economy, the market obeys the will of the buyer output, service must adapt to the needs and demands of the buyer. If it does not adapt, that is, if it does not produce a product worthy of demand, if it does not provide service, it may be damaged or even separated from its existence. Based on this, the abundance of goods and services is achieved. Freedom of prices plays an important role in ensuring the abundance of goods.

has its own characteristics in the coordination and management of activities. In it, self-management and state influence are mixed. The market economy, like any economy, develops as a result of the application of economic laws. On the one hand, these laws consist of general economic laws, and on the other hand, they consist of specific laws of the market economy. The market economy is a complex form of organization, operation, regulation and management of the economy, which is primarily based on commodity-money relations. Producers and consumers are connected through the market, and their cooperation is ensured through the market.

The market economy encourages everyone to think about the results of their activities, make calculations, and act rationally. Thus, if we want to give a brief definition of the market economy, it is as follows can be expressed: Market economy is a democratic economy based on commodity-money relations, freedom of economic activity, encouraging every person to think about the result of his activity and run a rational economy.

Since the market economy is based on commodity-money relations, it has an object and subjects.

The objects of the market economy represent what these relationships and relationships are about, and the subjects represent the relations and relationships between whom these relationships take place. The object of the market economy is goods and money.

A market economy is an economy based on commodity production. That is why the central category of the market economy is goods and money. Currently, money mass or aggregates are understood as another object of the market economy.

Subjects of the market economy.

Subjects of the market economy consist of entrepreneurs, workers, capital, owners of valuable securities, merchants, consumers, etc. These subjects have equal rights and are connected with each other in terms of their purpose, interests encouraging cooperation, the form and nature of organization of movement of goods and services.

The main subjects of the market economy are divided into four groups in the economic literature:

household, firm (enterprise), financial institution and state (government).

1. Household. Its composition consists of an economic unit - a family - consisting of one or several people.

Household:

a) provides production with labor resources;

- b) makes independent decisions;
 - c) is the owner of production factors: capital, land, labor, entrepreneurship;
 - g) strives to satisfy the needs of his own economy to the maximum extent .
2. Enterprises (farms , firms) are economic entities:
- a) use production factors for the purpose of producing any product or service ;
 - b) try to make the most of it;
 - c) work independently.
3. Financial institutions - normal operation of the market, enterprises is a finance, credit organization that regulates the movement of financial resources to ensure money mass.
4. The state, more precisely , all state offices, courts, and organizations. They control economic entities and the market to the extent necessary through legal and political authority to achieve a common goal . At the same time, it deals with production and consumption . Subjects of the market economy interact. Owners of labour, land, capital and other means sell them to enterprises and firms. They, in turn, use production factors to create goods and provide services.

Their interaction is as follows :

are producers (service providers) on the one hand, and consumers on the other. In the market, they appear as sellers and buyers .

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Graphics Processor and its Main Capabilities

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Abstract: Working with computer graphics is becoming one of the most popular areas in modern computer technology. Currently, even professional artists and designers are engaged in this direction. CorelDRAW is one of the most functional graphics programs.

Key words: program, Windows, CorelDRAW, image, computer.

The working window of CorelDRAW 10 is similar to the window of other graphic editors. When the CorelDRAW 10 program is launched, the initial dialog box of the program appears on the screen. It is also possible to cancel this mode in advance. This is done by removing the flag from the Show this Welcome Screen at startup line.

First, let's look at how to set up the program. If the working window does not occupy the full screen, click the expand button in the program title. As a result, the working window is created on the full screen, making it easier to work with the CorelDRAW 10 program.

In order for the created image to be clearly visible, and the controlled elements to be placed on the screen, it is recommended to use the allowed screen size of 1024x768 pixels, preferably 1280x1024. Let's get acquainted with the main elements of the CorelDRAW 10 vector graphics editor in the working window (Fig. 1). Like other programs running in the Windows environment, the window title and menu are located at the top of the window. In CorelDRAW 10, the possibilities of changing its interface have been expanded.

Picture 1. The working window of the program

In the center of the program window is a sheet image, which is called the working area. It is possible to draw in and out of the working area, but when printing, only the drawing in the working area is output. To manage colors, use the color bar on the right side of the window. In the status bar, various types of information are created that facilitate working with the editor. The main drawing tools are located in the toolbar. The buttons located in it ensure quick execution of actions performed in the editor. In particular, the Property Bar stands out. The buttons on it will appear or not, depending on the actions you are performing. At any time, you can find the properties of the button corresponding

to the current situation in the toolbar and place it on any side of the working window. At the same time, it is possible to change the position of the menu bar. Click the right mouse button on the empty part of the toolbar, as a result, the auxiliary menu (context) will appear (Fig. 2). An embedded flag in the helper window shows which sections are placed in the toolbar.

Figure 2. Help menu

The user can use various tools on the panel. Select the equipment in the panel one by one with the mouse and pay attention to its Property Bar (Property bar), their appearance will change according to each equipment. At the same time, the display of information in the status bar will also change. After the editor is configured, you can work with the image and create various vector objects.

Creating images in the CorelDraw graphic editor.

Image resolution is a property of an image, measured by the number of dots per inch (dpi). This unit is determined during image generation using a graphic editor or scanner. The value of the image capacity is stored in the image file and depends on another feature of the image - its actual size.

The actual size of an image is measured in pixels or length units (millimeters, centimeters, inches). It is defined during image generation and saved with the image file.

If you need to see the image on the screen, it is convenient to express its size in pixels. Because in this case it will be easy to determine what part of the screen the image occupies.

If you need to print an image on paper, it is convenient to express its size in units of length. Because in this case it will be easy to determine what part of the paper the image occupies.

Another feature of the image is the number of colors that can be used in it. That is, different images can have different color scales: black-and-white bar, halftone (shades of gray gradually passing from white to black), indexed color, full color.

Black and white line drawing. One bit of information is allocated to each pixel of the image. It is known that one bit can encode two states: white and black. This type of image is called Bitmap. The color scale of such an image is one bit.

Colorful image. A grayscale image pixel is coded with 8 bits, that is, its color scale is 8 bits. Each pixel of the image can take 256 different values. These values are called gray scale. This scale has 256 gradations of gray, each of which is represented by a light value ranging from 0 (black) to 255 (white). This is enough to accurately depict a black-and-white photograph.

Nowadays, There Are Programs With The Possibility Of 16-Bit Encoding Of The Image, With The Help Of Which It Is Possible To Create Images With 65,536 Different Shades Of Gray Instead Of 256. But When Saving Such Images, The File Size Is 2 Times Larger Than 8-Bit.

Working Window Elements Of Coreldraw 10 Editor. In The Vector Coding Method, Geometric Shapes, Curves And Straight Lines, Circles, Squares, Ellipses, Partial Images Are Stored In The

Computer Memory In The Form Of Geometric Abstractions Such As Mathematical Formulas. For Example, To Encode A Circle Shape, It Doesn't Have To Be In The Form Of Individual Pixels. It Will Be Enough To Store Its Radius, Center Point Coordinates And Color In Memory. For A Rectangle, It Is Necessary To Remember The Length Of Its Sides, Location And Color. Various Shapes Can Be Interpreted Using Mathematical Formulas. Several Simple Shapes Are Used To Draw Complex Shapes. For Example, We Paint A Rectangle With Arc-Shaped Corners In Black, And By Adding Three White Rectangles And One Black Rectangle To It, We Can Create A Three-Inch Diskette Picture (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. A vector image consisting of several parts.

All views in vector format consist of several parts, which can be changed independently of each other. These parts are called objects, and a new object is created using several objects. As a result, objects have a more complex appearance. In each object, their size, curvature and location values are given. Therefore, it is possible to change the appearance of images using simple mathematical operations. When using vector graphics, it is not taken into account that the size of the object is too small or, on the contrary, too wide. In both cases, working with the image is the same. You can zoom in or out at any time without changing the quality of the image. An important advantage of vector encoding is that the size of the graphic file is significantly smaller than the size of raster graphics files. However, vector graphics also have their drawbacks. First of all, it is very difficult to create a real image due to the conditionality of the created image, that is, the images consist of curves built using formulas. Therefore, vector graphics cannot be used for encoding images. If the image needs to be interpreted, the size of the resulting file will be much larger than the size of a raster graphic file.

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Maqom San'atiga E'tibor Milliy San'atimizga E'tibor

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada maqom san'atiga qaratilgan e'tibor hamda uni rivojlantirish milliy san'atimizni saqlab qolish va uni rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Buzruk, rost, navo, dugoh, segoh, iroq, YUNESKO, anjuman.

Maqom san'atning oliy turi darajasi sanaladi. Maqom kuyini tinglash uchun inson avvalo uning mazmun mohiyatiga tushunish darajasida bo'lmog'i lozim.

Shashmaqom forschadan tarjima qilinganda olti maqom degan ma'noni anglatadi. O'zbek va tojik xalqlari musiqiy merosida markaziy o'rin tutgan maqomlar turkumi: parda, ohang, usul, shakl, uslub kabi vositalar bilan o'zaro uzviy bog'langan mumtoz kuy va ashulalar majmui. U muayyan shartsharoitlarda musiqiy folklor hamda kasbiy musiqi yo'nalishlarida orttirilgan ko'p asrlik ilmiyijodiy tajriba hamda izlanishlar natijasida yuzaga kelgan. Shashmaqom milliy hamda mintaqaviy mumtoz musiqi an'alarining tarixan uzun taraqqiyot jarayoni natijasida bir qator bastakorlar avlodi san'atining qomusiy mahsulidir.

O'rta asr Yaqin va O'rta Sharq xalqlari musiqi ilmida maqom, asosan, parda tuzilmalari tushunchasini hamda ularga mos holda yaratilgan kuy va ashulalarni ifodaladi. Maqomlar dastlabki davrda tarqoq shakllarda rivojlandi, 13-asrda esa Safiuddin al-Urmaviy ularni o'n ikki asosiy maqomdan iborat nazariy tizim shakliga keltirdi. 17-asrdan so'ng O'n ikki maqom tizimi inqirozga uchrab, uning negizida Sharq xalqlari orasida maqomlarning yangicha milliy va mahalliy shakllari vujudga kela boshladi. Xususan, 18-asrning o'rtalarida O'rta Osiyoning yirik madaniy markazlaridan biri Buxoro shahrida saroy sozanda, xonanda va bastakorlari ijodiyijrochilik faoliyatida Shashmaqom uzilkesil shakllanib, Buxoro maqomlari, Buxoro Shashmaqomi nomlarida ham yuritildi.

O'zbek maqom turlaridan Xorazm maqomlari, Farg'onaToshkent maqom yo'llari, shuningdek, yovvoyi (erkin ko'rinishdagi) maqomlar, surnay, dutor yo'llari va boshqalar Shashmaqom ta'sirida rivojlandi. O'tgan zamon bastakorligida keng qo'llanilgan amal, kor, naqsh, peshrav, savt, tarona, qavl kabi janrlarning noyob namunalari Shashmaqom tarkibida bizgacha yetib keldi.

Maqomlar sozanda va xonandalar tomonidan yakka tarzda, shuningdek, jo'rovozlik va jo'rnavozlikda ijro etib kelingan. Xususan, Buxoro amirlari saroyida eng so'nggi davrda jo'rnavozlik asosan, 2 tanbur, 2 doira (doirachilar xonanda ham bo'lgan), afg'on rubobi, sato yoki qo'biz, imkonga ko'ra bo'lamon cholg'ularidan iborat bo'lgan. Maqom ijrochiligida tanbur yetakchi soz hisoblanadi. Chunki u torlarini maqom pardalariga moslab sozlashda va maqom yo'llarini mukammal yangratishta birmuncha qulayliklarga ega. Doira esa sozanda va xonandalarning Shashmaqom qismlarini belgilangan usul negizida ijro etishlari uchun zarur vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Xalqimiz madaniy merosining ajralmas qismi bo'lgan milliy maqom san'ati o'zining qadimiy tarixi, teran falsafiy ildizlari, betakror badiiy uslubi va boy ijodiy an'analari bilan ma'naviy hayotimizda alohida muhim o'rin egallaydi. Asrlar davomida ulug' shoir va olimlar, mohir bastakorlar, hofiz va sozandalarning mashaqqatli mehnati va fidoiyligi, ijodiy tafakkuri bilan sayqal topib kelayotgan ushbu noyob san'at nafaqat yurtimiz va sharq mamlakatlarida, balki dunyo miqyosida katta shuhrat va e'tibor qozongan.

Maqom san'atining gultoji bo'lgan "Shashmaqom" YUNESKO tomonidan insoniyatning nomoddiy madaniy merosi sifatida e'tirof etilgani hamda uning Rerezentativ ro'yxatiga kiritilgani buning yaqqol tasdig'idir. O'tgan davr mobaynida mamlakatimizda maqom san'atini o'rganish va rivojlantirish borasida muayyan ishlar amalga oshirildi. Ayniqsa, o'zbek "Shashmaqomi" nota matnlarining nashr etilishi va ularga muvofiq ravishda maqom kuy-qo'shiqlarining magnit lentalariga yozib olinishi ulkan ilmiy-madaniy ahamiyatga ega voqea bo'ldi.

Bugungi kunda yurtimizda Yunus Rajabiy nomidagi Maqom ansambli, hududlarda maqom ansambllari, O'zbekiston davlat konservatoriyasida shu yo'nalishda maxsus kafedra faoliyat ko'rsatayotgani, sohaga oid ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilayotganini qayd etish lozim. Ayni vaqtda milliy o'zligimizni anglash, madaniyatimizni har tomonlama rivojlantirish, xalqimiz, avvalo, yosh avlodimizni yuksak insoniy tuyg'ular ruhida tarbiyalash, uning estetik didi va tafakkurini shakllantirishda maqom san'atining keng imkoniyatlaridan yetarlicha foydalanilmayapti.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenting 2017-yil 17-noyabrdag PQ-3391-sonli qarori bilan o'zbek maqom san'atini dunyoga tarannum etish hamda ushbu san'at orqali xorijiy sayyohlarni jalb etish maqsadida Shaxrisabz shahrida an'anaviy tarzda "Xalqaro maqom san'ati" forumi o'tkazildi.

Shuningdek, mazkur qaror bilan, O'zbekiston milliy maqom san'ati markazi faoliyatini tashkil etish belgilandi. Shu yilda birinchi marta muvaffaqiyatli o'tkazilgan xalqaro forumga 73 ta mamlakatdan san'atkorlar tashrif buyurishdi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbusi bilan o'zbek milliy maqom san'atini yanada rivojlantirishga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar doirasida "Maqom" nomli kitob-albom nashr etildi. Kitobda mazkur san'atning falsafasi, Forobiy, Ibn Sino, Marog'iy, Kavkabi kabi allomalar asarlari, turli maqom yo'llari, jumladan, Buxoro Shashmaqomi, Xorazm Olti yarim maqomi va Dutor maqomi, Farg'ona-Toshkent maqomi tarixiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

"Tanbur chizg'ilari" deb nomlangan milliy nota yozuvining kashf etilishi hamda uning vositasida Olti yarim maqom, Dutor maqomlarining notalashtirilishi, shu bilan birga, o'tgan asr boshlarida maqomning ilk bora perfokartalarga muhrlanishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek, maqom ijrochiligida keng qo'llaniladigan sozlarni yasashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va texnologiyasi bayon etilib, mashhur ustalarning nomlari keltirilgan.

O'zbek xalqining ulkan musiqa merosining eng yuqori pog'onasida turadigan milliy musiqamizning oliy peshtoqi hisoblang "Shashmaqom"dir. Yurtdoshimiz bo'lgan Yunus Rajabiy ham "Shashmaqom" san'atiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan san'atkorlardan desak to'g'ri bo'ladi. Yunus Rajabiyning 1966-1975-yillarda yozib qoldirgan "Shashmaqom" haqidagi kitoblaridan yosh maqomshunos tadqiqotchi olimlar o'zlari uchun kerakli ko'plab ma'lumotlarni topishlari mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, hududlarda maqom san'atiga ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab-internatlarining faoliyatini yo'lga qo'yilishi, kelajak avlodni yoshligidan ushbu san'at turining sir-asrorlarini o'rganishi uchun imkoniyat desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi.

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Music Reflects Life

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Abstract: *Music has its own content, but it is given and created only in a specific form, specific means characteristic of this art, which can be given through water, color, movement and other means.*

Key words: *Music, word, work, listening.*

Fine art is close to poetry, dance and music, because they reflect life and human spirit. However, no matter how close the mood, character idea, and spirit are to each other, different works of art, even if they are the same in terms of the plot, still differ in the characteristics of their "languages".

Sometimes the title or program of a piece of music is considered its content. But no name, program can fully convey the musical content of a real work of art. This can also be seen from the fact that several composers create musical works that are close to each other and at the same time different from each other based on the same plot. Composers achieve this thanks to the infinite possibilities of music to reflect the most delicate feelings of imagination and character.

Expressing the content of the music in simple words does not fully reveal the essence of the work. But the science of musicology recognizes the possibility of describing the mood, meaning, general character of a musical piece. It is especially important in the organization of musical perception, especially in audiences with little musical training.

Although the description of the content of the music does not compensate for its impact, the description given to the period, the history of the creation of the work helps to be more careful while listening to the work, to understand it better, to understand it and to feel it.

The fact that music reflects life, its connection with life and its dependence on the composer's and performer's views on life makes music a means of education. The importance of the art of music in the education of the younger generation is great.

He said, "Just as gymnastics shapes the body, so music shapes the human language." V.A. Sukholikskiy Abu Nasr al-Faroabi describes the influence of music on the formation of personality: "this science is useful in the sense that, if the character of the person is out of balance, it educates, perfects those who are not perfect, preserves the balance of those who are in balance... This science is the health of the body. is also useful for

When the listener pays attention to the thoughts and feelings of the listeners, develops their musical and creative abilities, teaches them to understand, love and frame the work of art, only then will the great educational potential of music be realized.

Introducing students to the art of music helps to educate their aesthetic and moral qualities, to form their worldviews, aspirations, and inner experiences. Cultivating aesthetic qualities in children serves as an effective tool in improving their spiritual, aesthetic and moral world, perfecting noble qualities.

The main goal of musical education is the formation of musical culture, which is a component of human spiritual culture.

The concept of "musical culture" is quite broad. It includes the following:

- a) moral-aesthetic feelings and attitudes, musical tastes and desires;
- b) knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the transmission of the art of music, i.e. for performance, listening and perception;
- c) musical, creative abilities that ensure the success of musical activities.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are in front of the listener:

- connecting musical education with life;
- developing students' interest in the art of music;
- development of musical-artistic taste and interest in musical activities;
- formation of the range of knowledge and skills in music;
- development of artistic creativity during musical activities;
- moral-aesthetic education of the listeners through the artistic content of the works;
- instilling enthusiasm for profession, craft and craft in music lessons;
- strengthening the educational effect of music.

One of the leading tasks of playing music at school is

listening to singers is the education of musical culture, because today's singer is tomorrow's listener who has acquired interest and taste. Depending on how this listening music culture is formed, in the future, a person will improve his inner world through art, or accept music as a tool that opens up his personality. These tools require the listener to have a good knowledge of the subject and constant attention to the personality of the listener.

The above points show that we can understand musical education in two different ways. In a broad sense, musical education is the formation of a person's spiritual needs, that is, his constant pursuit of beauty and adherence to these rules of beauty in everyday life, his morals, consciousness and aesthetic appreciation of life reality. In this sense, musical education means human education.

In short, musical education is the development of a person's musical abilities, perception of music, that is, education of emotional sensitivity to music, understanding of the content of music, and deep feeling.

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Химическая Промышленность Узбекистана

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается состояние химической промышленности Республики Узбекистан. Сделан детальный обзор сырьевой базы химической промышленности Узбекистана и основных предприятий отрасли.

Ключевые слова: Химическая промышленность, предприятие, удобрение, производство.

Химическая промышленность — одна из важнейших отраслей тяжелой промышленности страны. С одной стороны, неуклонный рост нефтегазовой и угольной промышленности в республике (как следствие, расширение масштабов и географии химического сырья), с другой стороны, производство минеральных удобрений, различных химических, пластмасс, растущая потребность в искусственном волокне, синтетическом каучуке, лаке, кислоте и щелочи создали объективные условия для развития этой отрасли.

Следовательно, химическая промышленность страны, естественно, быстро развивается. Она быстро развивается, особенно в регионах, богатых сырьем топливно-энергетической отрасли.

Химическая промышленность страны производит более 750 видов продукции, в качестве сырья используются природный газ, нефть, уголь, сера, озокерит, различные полезные ископаемые, известняк, графит, а также отходы цветной металлургии и материалы хлопково-конопляной переработки. Узбекистан имеет чрезвычайно большие запасы поваренной и калийной соли, фосфорного и содового сырья, магния и натрия. Их основные рудники — Тубагатан, Байбичакан, Окпат, Ходжайкон, Лалмикон и другие.

Основной продукцией химической промышленности республики являются минеральные удобрения. Аммофос, аммиачная селитра, сульфат аммония, суперфосфат, карбамид, сжиженный аммиак, а также очень необходимые сельскому хозяйству комплексные азотные и фосфорные удобрения производятся на Чирчикском электрохимическом комбинате, Ферганские удобрения с азотом производятся на Самаркандском химкомбинате, Навои Ким и Алмалыкское объединение «Аммофос».

Страна полностью обеспечивает свои потребности в минеральных удобрениях, а определенная часть (в среднем равная 26-30 млн долларов США в год) экспортирует удобрения за рубеж. Однако калийные удобрения в Узбекистане не производятся. Поэтому Тубагатанский калийный комбинат строится на базе калийных солей в Кашкадарьинской области.

Гидролизные предприятия химической промышленности специализируются на производстве этилового спирта, фурфурола, пищевых дрожжей. Такими предприятиями являются Андижанский гидролизный завод, Ферганское фурановое объединение, Янгийский биохимический завод.[3]

В республике производство резинотехнических изделий осуществляется объединением «Узбекрезинотехника» в г. Ангрен, производство пластмассовых изделий осуществляется на Охангароне «Сантекстлит», Джизакском заводе пластиковых труб, Ташкентском компания "Рангли Лак", в г. Алмалык. Наманганский химический завод. Объединение «Узбекрезинотехника» специализируется на выпуске автомобильных шин с 1992 года. В 1996 году были запущены производственные мощности в размере 1,5 млн. шин для легковых автомобилей и 200 тыс. шин для грузовых автомобилей. [1,2]

Химия органического синтеза – одна из развивающихся отраслей химической промышленности республики. Положительное влияние на ее развитие оказывает рост газовой отрасли – в настоящее время крупнейшим предприятием в этой сфере является Навоийский химический завод. Он содержит мощности по производству ацетилена, уксусной кислоты, ацетилцеллюлозы, нитронового волокна. Ферганский и Наманганский химические заводы производят ацетатный и вискозный шелк. Эти искусственные волокна используются в производстве марли, ковров, трикотажа. [4]

Местно значимые отрасли химической промышленности специализируются на производстве лаков и бытовой химии. Предприятия химической промышленности города Ташкента, Лок-Боякский, Алмалыкский химический завод, выпускают различные стиральные порошки.

Химическая промышленность Узбекистана очень активно занимается производством новой продукции из местного сырья, автоматизацией переработки промышленных отходов, расширением экспортных возможностей химической промышленности, строительством совместных предприятий в кооперации с китайскими, американскими, японскими, немецкими и итальянскими компаниями на предприятиях и объединениях химической промышленности Узбекистана. В частности, быстрыми темпами строятся Кызылкумский фосфатный комбинат (мощностью 210 млн тонн), Кунгиротский завод едкого натра, Тубатаганский завод калийных удобрений, множество совместных предприятий.

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The Method of Drawing a Line-Constructive Drawing of a Cylinder in a Vertical Position on a Plane and a Step Drawing of a Cylinder Located Horizontally

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Abstract: *Drawing a cylinder consists of forming a perspective position of a circle. In the initial training, a thin model of the cylinder is placed on the table in an upright position. In this case, the cylinder should be located below the horizon line according to the artist's view.*

Key words: *pencil, geometric shape, artist.*

A cylinder is a geometric shape consisting of three surfaces: two flat, identical circles and one cylindrical surface connecting these circles. A frame model of a rectangle tied to a thread is used to show young artists the process of creating a cylinder shape. In this case, the rectangle is rotated and the image of the cylinder is formed. In the process of explaining the task, the axis of rotation (here, the axis of the cylinder) is always perpendicular to the base of the cylinder. According to the relationship between the height of the cylinder and the diameter of the base, cylinders can be of different types: high, low, elongated and other types of cylinders.

As mentioned above, it is necessary to start drawing geometric shapes lying on the horizontal axis from their base. Both bases of the cylinder are circles. We talked above about the transition of a circle to an ellipse according to its location on the horizon line. An ellipse is built on the basis of two mutually perpendicular axes: major (horizontal) and minor (vertical) axes. When they intersect, both should be divided into two equal parts.

Thus, the major axis of the ellipse lying on the horizontal plane, corresponding to the diameter of the circle, remains horizontal, and the length of this axis is determined by visually observing the ratios of the minor and major axes in a natural body. In this way, you can create a circle lying on the horizontal plane in the picture. For this, a perspective image of a square and its diagonals are used, and inside it an ellipse is marked with points.

While explaining the rules of drawing an ellipse, the pedagogue should warn the artists that the edges of the ellipse should not form sharp corners even when drawn in any case. An ellipse is a perspective view of a circle lying in a plane. Therefore, the lower axis of the ellipse is carefully moved from its lower part to its upper part even when its diameter is minimal.

Thus, the drawing of a cylinder begins by forming its base using the major or minor axis of the ellipse and the diagonal of the perspective square. First of all, a vertical axis is drawn, and with its help, the vertical position of the cylinder is determined, and as a result, it is possible to control the correct drawing of the shape. On this axis, the height of the cylinder is determined in relation to its width defined on the lower base. After that, the lower base ellipse is drawn and a vertical line is drawn from the estimated points on the base (based on the square and ellipse) up to the point on the specified upper base.

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The upper base of the cylinder is drawn taking into account the horizon line and the joining point. The upper ellipse is determined and vertical lines are drawn from the ends of the ellipses (the ends of the major axes of the ellipses) and these lines form the side surface of the cylinder. Here it should be remembered that a prism with a square base equal to the diameter of the cylinder base and the major axis was made to create the cylinder. After the cylinder is created, the excess guide lines can be softened with the eraser tool and the front parts of the ellipses, as well as the lines indicating the side of the cylinder, can be thickened by running the pencil.

The importance of depicting the perspective view of a circle and a cylinder is often felt in educational drawings during the drawing of geometric shapes and household appliances, and here it also serves as the central axis of reflection. In addition, the cylinder is a component of many complex shapes (including the human body). Therefore, it is necessary and mandatory to perform this task in the first period of formation of visual skills.

To draw a cylinder lying down, you need to first draw a prism lying horizontally with one side. In this case, the base of the prism is equal to the diameter of the base of the cylinder.

At the 1st stage, the general shape is lightly drawn with a pencil and the horizon line is marked to determine the compositional location of the model on the paper. After that, it is necessary to start drawing the prism from its base. Here, as a base, a right-angled rectangle is taken, the sides of which are equal to the height of the cylinder and the diameter of the circle on its base (20 a,b). This right-angled rectangle is the projection of the cylinder on the horizontal plane.

The artist starts drawing from the point closest to him, from the point where the sides of the rectangle meet. First, a perspective view of a rectangular prism is drawn.

To draw a cylinder lying on a horizontal plane, circles that serve as a base for the cylinder are drawn inside the squares that are the base of the prism. These circles are ellipses in perspective view.

It should be remembered that the circles that are the base of the cylinder are always perpendicular to the central axis, and this perpendicularity must be maintained when drawing the image of the body in any position relative to the artist. Therefore, the major axes of the ellipses drawn inside the square are drawn perpendicular to the axis of the cylinder. Comparison of these and minor axes of the ellipse is carried out by eye measurement in determining the "degree of openness of the circles" in perspective. The ellipses at the base are combined and the cylinder appears voluminous in width. In the process of

completing the picture, the cylinder lines are thickened, and as a result, the auxiliary lines move to the second level. 4 exercises. Drawing of an antique plaster jug in different positions relative to the horizon line and point of view. In these pictures, the views of the pitchers are depicted in different situations (reclining, tilted, standing). In all cases, the major axes of the ellipses are perpendicular to the central axis - the axis of symmetry - the axis of rotation of the pitcher.

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Combined Effect of Pesticides on the Cytogenetic Effect

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Abstract: *The genetic effect of pesticides is of no small importance for their combined effect on the body. Mature male laboratory mice were used in the experiments. The cytogenetic effect of pesticides was studied in the cells of the bone marrow and testicles using tests for accounting for a b e p p a t i o n of chromosomes in metaphase in bone marrow cells; micronuclei in polychromatophilic erythrocytes (PCE); aberrations of chromosomes in diakinesis - metaphase in testis cells.*

Key words: *genetic effect, pesticides, bone marrow, spermatocytes, chromosome aberrations, metaphase.*

INTRODUCTION. When assessing the genetic effect of pesticides, their combined effect on the body is of no small importance, since several pesticides can enter the human body at the same time during the use and storage of drugs . Moreover, pesticides can produce an additive (summed), synergistic (intensification) and antagonistic (weakening) effect. However, in the literature, data on the genetic effect of pesticides in their combined exposure are very rare. [1] Based on this, in this work, the cytogenetic effect of magnesium chlorate (defoliant), fosalone (insecticide), and cotorane was studied. (herbicide).

MATERIALS AND METHODS Mature male laboratory mice were used in the experiments. Animals were divided into 10 groups. First r p y p p a - control. Animals of the second, third and fourth groups were injected once separately with kotoran (330 mg/kg), fosalone (27 mg/kg) and magnesium chlorate (1745 mg/kg); animals of the fifth group - magnesium chlorate (1745 mg/kg) and phosalone (27 mg/kg) together once; the sixth group - three drugs together once; in experiments with the combined administration of drugs, the ratio of the volume of drugs was 1:1. Animals of the seventh, eighth and ninth groups were repeatedly (within 3 months) injected with magnesium chlorate (52 mg/kg), cotoran (10 mg/kg), phosalone (0.8 mg/kg); the tenth animal - magnesium chlorate (52 mg/kg) and phosalone (0.8 mg/kg) together; the eleventh animal - together with magnesium chlorate (52 mg/kg); fosalone (0.8 mg/kg) and kotoran (10 mg/kg).

RESULTS Data on the frequency of chromosome aberrations and the number of PChE with micronuclei in bone marrow cells of mice with separate and combined effects of kotoran , fosalone and magnesium chlorate with their single injection are given in Table. 1

Kotoran , fosalone and magnesium chlorate at a dose of $1/3 L D_{50}$, each with a separate single use, does not affect the genetic apparatus of mouse bone marrow cells. The frequency of xpo m oco m mutations (0.37; 0.35; 0.44%), as well as the number of PECs with micronuclei (1.14; 1.08; 0[^]83%) after the action of these pesticides were at the control level. Table 2 presents data on the frequency of chromosome aberrations and the number of PChE with micronuclei in bone marrow cells of mice after separate and combined action of kotoran , fosalone , and magnesium chlorate administered multiple times (within 3 months). With separate repeated administration of each pesticide, the frequency of chromosome aberration and the number of PChE with micronuclei increased by 6-7 times compared with the control. Such a frequency of chromosome aberrations and the number of PCEs with micronuclei were also observed in experiments in which animals were injected with combinations of two (magnesium chlorate + phosalone) and three (cotoran + fosalone + magnesium chlorate) pesticides in a ratio of 1:1.

Table 1. Chromosome aberration frequency and number of PChE *with* micronuclei in mouse bone marrow cells after separate and combined exposure to kotoran (330 ig /kg), phasalon a (27 mg/kg) and magnesium chlorate (1745 mg/kg) with their simultaneous administered

Table 1

Options	Number studied		metaphase with rearrangements		perestroika	
	Anim als	metaph ase	number	%	Total	per 100 metaphases
Control	8	731	3	0.41 +0.78-0.32	82	0.91±0.10
Apart						
Kotoran	8	540	2	0.37+0.96-0.32	103	1.14+0.11
Fazalon	9	857	3	0.35+0.67-0.27	97	1.08+0.10
Magic chlorate	9	681	3	0.44+0.84-0.34	75	0.83±0.3
Combined						
Phasalon+chl . magnesium	7	454	2	0.44+1.14-0.38	78	0.87+0.10
Kotoran + fazalon + chl . magnesium	8	769	4	0.52+0.81-0.37	85	0.94±0.10

CONCLUSION

However, under the action of chemical mutagens, including pesticides with mutagenic properties, there is a “saturation limit” in the appearance of chromosome aberrations, i.e. with an increase in the dose, duration of action of pesticides and combinations of pesticides, the frequency of chromosome aberrations does not increase in the future, therefore, it is very difficult to characterize the dose dependence of the appearance of chromosome aberrations in combination.

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Islam Karimov is the Founder of Independent Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article is about the founder of our independence, Hero of Uzbekistan, State and Political figure, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan and First Secretary of the Communist Party of the USSR before the declaration of independence of Uzbekistan. It is dedicated to I.A.KARIMOV, the President of Uzbekistan from 1991 until the end of his life, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: President, Commander, Politics, Person, Evacuation, Alternative, Institutions, Aphorism, Plumber, Ideology, Stable, Prosperity, Ground, Mangu.

Under the leadership of Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, Uzbekistan got its own Constitution, was recognized at the UN, and had equal relations with the CIS countries. The most important thing is that after our country gained independence, our identity, abilities, and traditions were restored. On this basis, representatives of the mature generation worthy of our Motherland, Independence, and Future began to grow up. I.A. Karimov, a great statesman and politician, was born on January 30, 1938 in the city of Samarkand in the family of an ordinary servant. In his family, daily hard work was the only way to earn money for living. His childhood coincides with the war and post-war years. Despite the fact that he and all his relatives knew the true value of bread, they experienced hardship and deprivation, they shared their home and salt bread with the people who were evacuated in Uzbekistan during the Second World War, like thousands of our compatriots. In 1945, Islam Karimov entered the 21st school named after A.S. Pushkin in Samarkand and graduated with a gold medal. During his school years, he read a lot of literature, especially literature on history. He liked exact sciences, was interested in chess modeling and table tennis. He received education without separating it from production. I. Karimov graduated from many educational institutions and universities and worked as a leader in many state agencies.

On June 23, 1989, I.A. Karimov was elected the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and took over the management of Uzbekistan at the time of the tragic events. On March 24, 1990, at the session of the Supreme Soviet, I.A. Karimov was elected the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. He was elected as the President of the Republic and received an absolute majority of votes each time. This was observed on January 9, 2000, December 23, 2007, and March 29, 2015.

The activity of Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov has been elevated at the international level.

Medal of Honor of the President of Ukraine 2002.

"For services to the Republic of Italy" Cavalry Order of Cotta Cross (Italy) 1997.

Order of Mugunhwa, Republic of Korea, 1995.

"Altin Iron" Golden Eagle Order of Kazakhstan 1997.

Order of "Dono Yaroslov the Wise" Ukraine, 1998.

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Order of "Great Vytautas" (Lithuania)

2002.

Order "For Civil Services" (Spain) 2003.

Order "For Services" first class (Poland) 3003.

Order of "Golden Rune" (Georgia) 2003.

Order of "Staro Planina" (Bulgaria) 2003.

Order of "Haloskor" (Greece)

2003.

"Turkmenistanyn Derty il yasulusy" (Turkmenistan) October 2007.

Order of "Three Stars" (Latvia) 2008.

Presidential Order of "Courage" (Georgia) 2013.

Order of "Magtymguly International Bayragy" and "Makhtumquli" international award (Turkmenistan)

During the years of independence, the appearance of our country, cities and villages changed radically. In fact, Uzbekistan can be said to be a large construction area. Every year, new industrial enterprises are put into operation, educational institutions, healthcare facilities, and other social facilities are being built. Special attention is being paid to the construction of houses, which are expanding in size. On the initiative of I.A. Karimov, in order to create modern housing conditions close to urban conditions for rural residents, a program of individual housing construction was adopted in rural areas with the allocation of long-term mortgage credits on preferential terms. Islam Karimov is a wise President. Many words and thoughts of I.A. Karimov are aphorisms and are so deep in meaning that millions of our compatriots become the basis of mental peace, the moral basis of life. The principle helps to maintain peace and international harmony. Islam Abduganiyevich brought respect to the spiritual abilities of our people, preservation and development of our holy religion, traditions and customs, and our priceless historical heritage to the level of state policy. The President was the initiator of the process of spiritual revival, strengthening of the national identity, restoration of the historical memory of our nation, development of its great scientific and cultural potential. This ensures the development of Uzbekistan.

These noble works of I.A. Karimov did not go unnoticed, and he received the following prestigious awards:

"Avicenna" gold medal of UNESCO, 1998.

Gold and silver medals of UNESCO "2750th anniversary of Samarkand".

"Borobodur" gold medal of UNESCO.

"Silk Road" silver medal of UNESCO.

UNESCO medals dedicated to the anniversaries and commemorative dates of the cities of Fes (Morocco), Istanbul (Turkey).

"Aristotle" by UNESCO.

Gold Medal of the World Intellectual Property Organization, 1996.

Order of the First Class of the Russian Orthodox Church "Svyatoi Blagoverniy Knyazyia Daniila Moskovsdogo" (Russia)

1998.

Gold medal of the International Aviation Committee, 1999.

Gold medal of the Spanish Senate, 2003.

"Apostle Andrey Pervozvanny" has a gold star and the Order of the Forum.

"Dialogue of Cultures" prize of the World Social Forum (Russia) 2003.

International Award Foundation Order of St. Nicholas of Chudotvorets First Class (Ukraine) 2004.

"Honorary citizen of Seoul" (Republic of Korea) 2006.

"Sheikh-ul-Islam" (Azerbaijan) of the Scientific and Religious Council of the Administration of Caucasian Muslims, 2011.

Islam Karimov was a beloved son, husband, father and grandfather. He remembered his parents with great affection and warmth, especially his mother Sanobar. He would respect his six brothers. He was always grateful to his only sister, Mehrinisa. Since his school years, he has read a lot of books, and his school essays were an example for his classmates. They remember that he often stayed after classes to help those in need. Islam Abduganiyevich was a loyal friend and, depending on the opportunity, continued to communicate with his friends at school and institute despite his busy schedule. The memories of one of his classmates who currently live in Kozon are interesting. Describing his school years, he told a story about an incident that shows his personal qualities. When one of the elders asked the children what they wanted to be in the future during the fruit harvest, most of them said professions such as pilots and aviators. Young Islam's answer surprised both the children and the adults. leader. The sincere intentions of our great-grandfather as a child were reflected in the future

Honorable I.A. Karimov left immortal masterpieces for us and future generations. His works:

1. Uzbekistan: "National Independence, Economy, Politics, Ideology".
2. "Let us have a free and prosperous country."
3. "Homeland is as sacred as a place of worship."
4. "From the creative year".
5. "A new way of thinking and working is the demand of the times."
6. "Towards security and sustainable development".
7. "We build our future with our own hands."
8. "A free and prosperous homeland, a free and prosperous life is our ultimate goal."
9. "Each of us is responsible for the development of the country."
10. "It is necessary to fight for security and peace."
11. "The path we have chosen is the path of democratic development and cooperation with the enlightened world."
12. "Our peace and security and strength depend on our unity and determination."
13. "The Uzbek people will never be dependent on anyone."
14. "Man, his rights and freedoms are the supreme power."
15. "Liberating our society, deepening reforms, raising our spirituality and raising the standard of living of our people is the criterion and goal of all our work."

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16. "Towards modernization of the country and sustainable development of our economy".
17. "Ensuring the gradual and stable development of our patriotism is our highest goal."
18. "Towards overcoming the consequences of the global crisis, modernizing our country and raising it to the level of developed countries".
19. Deepening of democratic reforms and formation of civil society is the main criterion for the development of our country.
20. "Our way is to deepen the democratic reforms and to continue the Modernization processes consistently."
21. "This is the way to resolutely continue the improvement and modernization of our country."
22. "Uzbekistan's achievements and milestones are a confirmation of the path of reforms we have chosen."
23. "Raising the reforms we have started without limiting ourselves to the achieved milestones to a new level is our most urgent task today."
24. "High spirituality is an invincible power."
25. "It is the highest happiness to serve our motherland in the way of its happiness, fortune and great future."
26. "A nation that has breathed enough of the air of freedom will never turn back from its path."
27. "The people of Kashkadarya, who have overcome the trials of life, are capable of achieving any high goal."

Future generations are lovingly reading these works.

He had three children and six grandchildren, and communication with them brought him great joy.

His wife, Tatiana Akbarovna, was his true friend, helper, like-minded person, happily married to Islam Abduganiyevich for 47 years and shared all the hardships of life with him.

Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, the founder of our independent state, died on September 2, 2016 at 20:55 in Tashkent due to a stroke. Sincere love and deep respect for the first President was especially strongly manifested during the days of mourning. At that time, all our people escorted our President to his final destination with tears. About 60 years ago, a young talented boy who graduated from school with a gold medal was taken away from this city by fate, and now he has returned to his native land as an independent President of Uzbekistan. The death of Islam Abduganiyevich was a very heavy and irreparable loss for all residents of our Republic.

I.A. Karimov wanted to be buried in the land of his mother Samarkand, and his will was fulfilled. On September 3, 2016, the first President of Uzbekistan was buried in the ancient Hazrat Hizr Mosque of his small hometown of Samarkand.

He was working on his speech dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the Independence of Uzbekistan. I.A. Karimov wanted to end his speech with the following words. He did not have time to say these words. Now these words live forever in the hearts of our people.

"MAY THE CREATOR HIMSELF HELP IN ALL OUR GOOD WORKS, HIMSELF HELP! OUR COUNTRY PEACE, OUR SKY CLEAR, OUR PEOPLE SAFE! OUR INDEPENDENCE BE ETERNAL!!"

Our first President I.A. Karimov lived for his people throughout his life, and thanks to these good deeds, he will forever remain in the hearts of the people of Uzbekistan.

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The Value of Time

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Abstract: *This article discusses the role of the gift of time in people's lives, its value and impact on human life. Appreciating every second, learning and reading a lot of books creates the basis for the realization of the hidden potential of a person. In life, it is considered that each person can use time correctly and distribute it correctly in order to find his place.*

Key words: *time, science, knowledge, opportunity, blessing, life, moment, life, world, purpose.*

When a person is born, lives and spends his life, he is given countless blessings and riches. One of these blessings is called time. Man is given the opportunity to welcome a new day every morning. The time from morning to night is at his disposal. This is 1,440 minutes or 86,400 seconds of golden opportunity given to every person in the world. Have we ever felt that every day these moments are passing by, the precious moments of our dear life, the moments that are constantly falling apart? To us, time is simply the spinning of clock hands against endless numbers. But the constant spinning of these miles is a lifelong struggle with us. And this struggle is our whole life. We need to understand the role of the gift of time in people's lives, its high value and impact on human life. There are two blessings in the world that many people miss and appreciate late. One of them is health, and the other is free time. Loving life means appreciating time. Because life is created from time. Time is the most valuable thing in human life. A person can find lost things during his life, wealth, property, house. But the time that has passed can never be turned back and cannot be replaced. As long as a person lives in this world, he Until the last day of his life, he believes in his own strength and capabilities and looks for ways to achieve his dreams and goals. For this, each person needs a certain amount of time. Time is given to everyone, but a person who appreciates time makes good use of it.

So, if we think deeper, very few people use the great gift called time properly. Time is sharp and cutting like a sword. Every passing moment is more valuable than gold and dice. We should spend it on useful things. If we think deeply about the importance of our time, which is more valuable than these gold coins, we will feel how valuable it is. Every passing moment, every moment is a part of human life and life. As long as a person lives in this world, it would be appropriate to summarize the time he spends from birth to the end of his life. Every day, week, month and year summarizing his life, that is, a person should ask himself, what good thing did I do today, or what bad thing did I do. It is permissible to increase the benefit and reduce the damage as much as possible. Time is never neutral, it works for or against a person. A person's life passes in the blink of an eye. The fact that the days are passing by so quickly means that our life is coming to an end like a wind, minute by minute, second by second. Each passing day is a fair measure of our dear life. Time is such a precious thing

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that it cannot be worried about tomorrow. we don't even notice that the morning has passed like a wind.

How we spend our time is up to us. We are encouraged by our victories, draw conclusions from our failures, and strive for success again. Time is a priceless tool that reminds us that life goes on. The best time is to spend your life doing useful things. The worst time is the time spent in laziness and laziness. Time is a claim to heal our pain.

When do the days go slowly? Have we ever thought? When we are sad and worried, when we are sick, our days seem to pass slowly in our imagination. When we are happy, time flies like the wind. It is clear from today's day that we spend a lot of time on unnecessary things, and we have to do the necessary things. In fact, there are many more conveniences in modern times than in the past. The biggest mistake people make today is the wrong use of time. People who use their time correctly are the owners of many achievements. It is a good thing that every person does to himself that he spends his time in useful work without wasting it. If we mean useful things, let's take learning as an example. Human dignity increases with knowledge. Scientific people can give an impartial assessment of any events. Hakim Luqmoni says that there is no better friend in the world than knowledge. Knowledge is better than treasure. Because you need to take care of the treasure. And knowledge will save and protect you. In order for a person to find his place in life, it is necessary for him to acquire knowledge and to be able to do Riyazat. Learning, reading a lot of books creates the basis for the realization of the hidden potential of a person. It is important that people who are thirsty for knowledge, who can use opportunities widely, who spend their time in a planned way, will be able to achieve their goals. Acquiring knowledge protects a person from depravity, ignorance, and harmful actions.

In the 21st century - the age of globalization, new discoveries have both positive and negative effects on human life. In this age, whoever does not work on himself more and more, is behind the times, which in turn leads to wasted time. Today, we certainly look with envy at people who have achieved great success in their field, are masters of their craft, and are businessmen. Analyzes of their activities show that one of the main keys to their success is their ability to allocate time correctly and use it effectively. Nowadays, the development of science is developing, and at the same time, we are living in an age of advanced techniques and technologies. It is clear as day that our free time is spent in front of television, computer, mobile communication devices. It is no secret that people who get used to these devices do not even know how their time has passed. Roughly speaking, even eating is forgotten. True, the useful aspect of these tools, their role in our life is gaining importance. It makes our distance close and our difficulty easy. We just need to know how to use it properly. But it steals our precious time. We don't even pay attention to it. Are we able to make full use of our time in an age of many opportunities and conveniences? If we compare the recent war years with our present time, we can see it. Avloni, Cholpon, Hamza, Qadiri, etc., such people of knowledge were exposed to many humiliations, sufferings and difficulties. In their time, there were not as many books, libraries, schools, higher education institutions, educational centers for learning as there are now. But they even gave their lives to distribute food to the whole society, open schools, publish books, and make their people spiritual and enlightened. Opening a school or publishing a book was their highest goal in life. Souls familiar with such knowledge have grown up in our country. Talking about such people, we remembered only a drop from the sea.

Therefore, we young people should also be the owners of knowledge worthy of them. Because the blood of Baburs, Nawais, Timurids, Berunis flows in our blood. Uzbekistan is the land of such mature scientists, thinkers, sages, people of knowledge. The time has come for us to introduce our identity, our Uzbekism to the world. Our honorable President is creating conditions for us to raise the Uzbek flag in every field, on every front. Using these opportunities wisely, we will surely build the

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state that our countryman dreams of together. First of all, we need to use our time in a planned way in order to achieve our ambitious goals.

A person comes to life once, he is not given another chance, it is up to us how we spend our life.

If you want to know the value of a lifetime - ask a butterfly.

If you want to know the value of ten years, ask a thirty-year-old disabled person who became disabled in his twenties.

If you want to know the value of a year - ask the student who failed the exam.

If you want to know the value of one month, ask a mother whose child was born at eight months.

If you want to know the value of a day, ask the farmer whose harvest was left in the autumn rain.

If you want to know the value of an hour, ask a well-behaved child who came home an hour late.

If you want to know the value of five minutes, ask the passenger who was five minutes late for the train.

If you want to know the value of a tenth of a minute, ask the driver who brings the patient to the hospital.

In conclusion, it should be said that a person should appreciate every hour, every minute, every moment of his life. When a person uses his time effectively, he can protect himself from grief, pain, and life's worries. Because he spends his free time on useful activities. Life goes by like water. When our hair turns white and our face becomes wrinkled, when life suddenly sticks a cane in our hand, when our eyes lose their light, we realize that life has passed in the blink of an eye. That's how we begin to summarize our lives. When we make this summary, let's appreciate our precious time and spend it on useful things so as not to use sentences like, ehh... attang... Life is a priceless gift entrusted to us by God. Betrayal is a big mistake.

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Тупроқ Унумдорлигида Сидерат Экинларнинг Таъсири

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Аннотация: *Ҳар қандай қишлоқ хўжалиги экини экиш ва унинг нормал ривожланиши тупроқ қатлами таркибига боғлиқ. Тупроқ барча тирик организмлар учун ҳаёт манбаи ҳисобланади. Кейинги йилларда ер шарида яшовчи одамлар сонининг ошиши ва биосферга бўлаётган антропологик омилларнинг таъсири натижасида ер ёки тупроқ энг зарар кўрмоқда. Тупроқ унумдорлиги камайиб бораётганлиги таъшишли бўлиб қолмоқда.*

Ҳозирги давр талабидан келиб чиқиб, тупроқ унумдорлигини сақлаш ва оширишда қишлоқ хўжалиги экинларини алмашлаб экиш, унга мунтазам роия этиш ўта мўҳим вазифа ҳисобланади. Йўқотилган тупроқ унумдорлигини тиклаш, ошириш учун фермер хўжаликларидан асосий эътиборни кузги бўғдой анғизига экиладиган сидерат, такрорий ва оралиқ экинларга қаратиш, ўтмишдош экин сифатида ғўза ва кузги бўғдойга мос келадиган, тупроқ унумдорлигини оширадиган, озиқ-овқат маҳсулотлари ишлаб чиқариш ҳажмини кўпайтирадиган чорва моллар учун тўйимли ем-хашак бўла оладиган сабзавот, полиз, дон ҳамда дон-дуккакли экинларни етиштиришга алоҳида эътибор бериш зарур.

Дунё микёсида сидерат экинлар бўйича турли хил ижобий фикрлар мавжуд бўлиб, шундан Германиянинг Бонн шаҳридаги ўсимликчилик илмий-тадқиқот институтининг илмий ходими В. Volger (1979)нинг фикрича, оралиқ экинларни алмашлаб экиш тизимларига мунтазам киритиш тупроқ унумдорлигини сақлаш ва ошириб боришда муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Оралиқ экинлар сидерат сифатида хайдаб юборилганидан сўнг тупроқнинг хайдалма қатламида ўсимлик қолдиқларининг майдаланиши натижасида ҳар гектар ерда 30-60 кг. азот тўпайди ва кейинги экиладиган асосий экинни озиқланиши учун ижобий шароит яратиб берилади.

Шунингдек, тупроқдаги озиқа элементлари кузги ва қишки ёгин-сочинлар таъсирида тупроқнинг пастки қатламларини ювилиши жараёнини олдини олади.

Сўнги йилларда қишлоқ хўжалигида тупроқ унумдорлигини сақлаб қолиш, тиклаш ва оширишда ҳукумат томонидан да сидерат экинлардан фойдаланиш бўйича амалга ошириладиган чора-тадбирлар дастури тасдиқланган.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 28 январдаги “Қишлоқ хўжалиги экинлари уруғчилигини янада ривожлантириш бўйича чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги 106-сон қарорида белгилаб қуйилганки, 2022-2025 йилларда пахта майдонларида тупроқ унумдорлигини ошириш ва ғўзани минерал ўғитлар билан озиқлантиришни тўғри йўлга

кўйиш мақсадида: тупроқ унумдорлиги ва ҳосилдорлиги паст бўлган пахта майдонларида «ғўза+беда+ғалла» алмашлаб экиш тизимини жорий қилиш ва ҳар гектар майдонга 15 — 20 тонна органик ўғит ёки 20 — 30 тонна компост солиш ва дуккакли дон, сидерат экинлари экиш.

Шунингдек, 2022 йил 25 мартдаги “Пахта майдонларида тупроқ унумдорлигини ва ҳосилдорликни ошириш, суғоришнинг янги технологияларини жорий этишни қўллаб-қувватлаш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги 179-сон қарори ижросини таъминлаш мақсадида тупроқ унумдорлигини оширишда оралик ва сидерат экинлар тури ва навларини танлаш ва экиш, илмий асосланган алмашлаб ва навбатлаб экиш бўйича тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилиб, худудларда қишлоқ хўжалиги махсулот етиштирувчилар учун семинарлар ўтказилмоқда.

Умуман олганда, сидератлардан фойдаланиш тупроқ структурасини оптималлаштириш, унинг физик ва физик-кимёвий хоссаларини сифат жиҳатдан ўзгартириш (намлик сиғими ортади, буферлик, кислоталилик камаяди ва бошқалар.). Бундан ташқари, сидератлардан фойдаланиш туфайли фойдали тупроқ микрофлорасининг фаолияти фаоллашади. Сидератлар тупроқ шамол ва сув турлари эрозиясидан ҳимоя қилади, шунингдек, озикланиш майдони учун бегона ўтлар билан рақобатлашади, унинг ўсишини бостиради.

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Proportion of Means of Expression in Gafur Gulam's Stories

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Abstract: *One of the authors who deserves a prominent place in the history of 20th-century Uzbek literature is Gafur Gulam. His contributions as a novelist, literary critic, translator, and academic poet are still relevant today.*

Gafur Gulam endured a very challenging existence. In 1912, he lost his father, and two years later, his mother. When his parents abandoned him at age 15, G. Gulam had to care for his three orphaned sisters on his own and support them financially. He is therefore required to complete numerous jobs. The pages of Gafur Gulam's difficult existence include selling fresh fruit, working as an apprentice cobbler, hauling, guarding, tinsmithing, typing, teaching, and tutoring. In numerous poems and short stories, Gafur Gulam recalls his life as an entrepreneur and his exploits:

Isitma aralash

Qo'rqinch tush kabi

Xayol ko'zgusidan

*O'chmaydi sira*¹

In the depths of his heart, the memories that persisted in that "mirror of imagination" continued to cause him grief. When he observes acts of generosity, genuine affection, considerate individuals, and more:

Otalik hissining

Bebahi, laziz

To'lqinlari ichra

G'arq bo'lib ketib... (Vol 2. 23 p.)

When the poet was a child, he could address the entire human species and say things like, "Calm down, my liver," "Don't worry, my lamb," "Thank you, knock on my head," "Why are you scared?" and "You are in your own home."

In the 1920s, Gafur Gulam joined the Turkestan Education Commissariat's campaign to gather orphaned kids. He was employed as a manager and teacher in an orphanage (boarding school) that was established for 150 kids and is run by the Urfon school. He was unable to ignore the plight of orphans and recognizes some parallels in his own experience. The poet's first poem was composed at an orphanage amid real-life circumstances. The poet did not feel that it was necessary to publish it since he was not happy with it.

¹ Гафур Ғулом. Мукаммал асарлар тўплами. 12 томлик. Т.2. -Т.: Фан, 1984, - Б.22

In his journalistic efforts, G. Gulam gave particular attention to the destiny of children who have lost their primary provider. He exhorted all comrades in his writing, "Let's not forget our brothers," to collect orphans, which was a noble and good work.

"May your smile be dazzling," "May the sun of your life shine on your forehead," "Fly on the ceiling of the earth, my daughter, far from tiredness," and "Rejoice, beloved sons" are some of the good wishes that Gafur Ghulam was able to convey to future generations. For this reason, in reaction to a radio transmission from Berlin, he wrote the poem "I Am a Jew.":

Inson irqidanman,

Inson millati (Vol. 2. 17 p.)

is built upon the idea of humanity. Of course, there are several examples of this kind in a scholar's poetry. All of Gafur Ghulam's works, especially his prose, exhibit this trait in a blatant way.

The literary critic S. Mamajonov quotes Oybek in his analysis of Gafur Gulom's brief prose: "Gafur captures the image of individuals in his stories skillfully. He has the ability to understand the psychology of his supporting cast members. It sees their ideas, opinions, objectives, and aspirations in a limited way"².

Aiming for a life of freedom, Mukarrama and Ibay in Nasir's 1928 story "Girl" attempt to decide what will happen to the girl's parents, Shakir brother and Zulaiho aunt. They keep potential suitors away from the boy. If my mother and father are not displeased, it will be enough, Mukarrama thinks as he and his girlfriend leave his father's home. He misses his parents while leading a tranquil life in Andijan. Stomping on their faces while apologizing for his actions and claiming that "my face is dirty," he does so. It is extremely wonderful to see the goodness of a parent who reads Mukarrama's letter and realizes that his child is safe and content. Brother Shakir adds, "May God grant you a white path," and aunt Zulayho responds, "If I may see all three souls in good health," expressing her longing and hope.

Repentance on the part of the girl and sympathy on the part of the parents seem to be limmo-lim. Verse 23 and verse 24 of Surah Al-Isra of the Holy Qur'an mention that one of the fundamental obligations of every individual is to honor their parents throughout their lives. A child must first love his mother if he is to treat his parents with respect. After all, "Mothers are paradise's feet." The moms of many scholars, scholars, and flawless persons were educated women, and they set an example for their children with their impeccable lives, according to Mrs. Annemarie Schimmel, a German historian of Islam³.

In reality, a mother's role and duty to raise her children are of the utmost importance in Muslim culture. Because of this, our poets and authors pay close attention to how mothers are depicted in their works. The variety of ways that moms are interpreted in Ghafur Ghulam's stories and stories demonstrates the writer's talent. The author's creativity in this area is more obvious in the aforementioned novella "The Girl." In the story, Nasir takes a poetic detour and extols the virtues of a mother's love:

«The tenderness of a nursing mother cannot be matched by any other touch. Mothers are revered for their dedication to raising their children. Futures are fashioned by all mothers. The "goddesses" of civilization are all moms...»⁴ (Vol. 6. 16 p.) If you pay attention, we are discussing "all moms," or the female race, in addition to the story's heroes. This is also the writer's mother's, who passed away at the age of 36, cry, which is not one of love.

² Қаранг: Мамажонов С. Ғафур Ғулом прозаси. Т. : Фан, 1966, 50 б.

³ Аннемарие Шиммел. Жонон менинг жонимда. Олмон тилидан Йўлдош Парда таржимаси. Т. : Шарқ, 1999, 84 б.

⁴ Қаранг: Ғафур Ғулом. Мукамал асарлар тўплами. 6 т. Т. : Фан, 1986

It appears that Ghafur Ghulam used vibrant visual tools in balance to make sure that his stories were successful.

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Develop and Apply a Questionnaire to Determine Dental Compliance in Patients with Epilepsy

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Abstract: *Dental pathology in patients with mental and psychosomatic disorders (A.P. Chechel, 1968; Banchenko G.V. 1979; Petrikas A.Zh., 1987; Krekshina V.A. et al., 1991; Zenovsky V.P., 2004). The treatment of mentally ill patients is due to the lifelong use of psychotropic drugs (neuroleptics, anticonvulsants, antidepressants, etc.), which alter the functions of the autonomic nervous system and cause metabolic and endocrine disorders (Morozov G.V., 1988, Avrutsky G.Ya., 1988, Mashkovsky M.D. 1993).*

In recent years, the population of patients with epilepsy has been increasing. Therefore, the issues of their quality of life become one of the most important problems (Geht A.B., 2000). At the same time, according to the literature, the state of the oral cavity and the prevalence of dental pathology in patients with epilepsy, despite the importance of this problem and its relevance, have not been studied enough. Most of the works of domestic and foreign authors are devoted to the phenomenon of hypertrophic gingivitis in epilepsy patients taking diphenin (A.P. Chechel, 1968; Abramov N.M., Osorina E.P. 1964; Makhtai E. et al., 1998; Kimball O.R. 1939, Penarrocha-Diago M, Bagan-Sebastian J.V, Vera-Sempere F., 1990). Studies of the state of the oral cavity were conducted without taking into account the dynamics of the disease and the clinical severity of personality changes and are outdated. (A.P. Chechel, 1968; A.A. Nechaeva, 1971).

Recently, the question of compliance in dental practice in providing care to patients has been raised (Trezubov V.N., Neznamov G.G., 1989; Becher V. et. al., 1988; Mendoza A.R., 1991; P. Checci, 1994; Demetroiou N., 1995; M.Rzewuska, 2002). This is due to the fact that without interaction between the doctor and the patient, it is impossible to achieve positive effects from the ongoing therapeutic and preventive measures.

Comprehensive studies devoted to assessing the condition of the oral cavity, clarifying the pathogenetic mechanisms of dental and periodontal diseases, as well as data on the study of compliance in such a socially significant category of mental patients as patients with epilepsy.

It is well known that the main pathological processes - dental caries, gingivitis and periodontitis are most often caused by the accumulation of cariesogenic and gingivopathogenic microflora on the surface of the teeth and especially in the interdental spaces (Kuskova V.F., Rebreeva JT.H. 1971; Adkina G.V. 1984; Rumyantsev V.A., 1997). Effective hygiene of the oral cavity and interdental spaces is the prevention of the occurrence and development of more severe forms of dental and periodontal diseases (Groholsky A.P., 1995; Kychakova S.I., 1993; Honkala E., 1990; Chistova T.A., 2001). Especially relevant is the implementation of hygienic measures in the conditions of a neuropsychiatric hospital.

The aim of the study is a comprehensive study of the state of the oral cavity in patients with epilepsy and optimization of oral hygiene in conditions of neuropsychiatric.

Research objectives

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To study the features of the oral cavity in patients with epilepsy.
2. To identify the frequency of hypertrophic gingivitis in patients with epilepsy taking diphenin.
3. To establish the relationship between the degree of proгредиency of the epileptic process and dental indicators in patients with epilepsy.

An oral irrigator has been introduced for the first time to optimize oral hygiene in the conditions of inpatient treatment of mentally ill patients, including patients with epilepsy. For the first time, the effectiveness of its use in psychiatric patients undergoing inpatient treatment by local pH-metry has been shown, in connection with which the irrigator can be recommended for widespread use in order to improve the hygienic condition of the oral cavity in this contingent of patients. A model has been developed to optimize the interaction of participants in the provision of dental care to the mentally ill, including patients with epilepsy.

Conclusions

1. In the structure of the CPI index in patients with epilepsy, the dominant number of extracted teeth was revealed. Inflammatory periodontal diseases in patients with epilepsy are more common than in the control group. Unsatisfactory oral hygiene and high need for prosthetics (76%) were revealed. The rate of stimulated salivation is reduced (0.67 ± 0.05 ml/min), and the pH of the oral fluid has a slightly acidic medium (6.54 ± 0.04 pH units).
2. Among epilepsy patients taking diphenin, hypertrophic gingivitis in the form of mild clinical manifestations was observed in 31.3% of cases.
3. The level of dental health in all dental indicators in patients with epilepsy with moderate personality changes is higher than in patients with pronounced personality changes.

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Процесс Фильтрации Грунтовых Вод

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Аннотация: Карьеры любой глубины и площади, создаваемые для открытой разработки полезных ископаемых (угля, руды и т.д.) изменяют, природный потенциал не только верхней части литосферы, но и атмосферы и гидросферы. В статье рассмотрено состояние исследовательских работ, по созданию модели фильтрования грунтовых вод на сегодняшний день. Рассмотрены некоторые модели и системы облегчающие исследовательскую деятельность и фильтрацию грунтовых вод.

Ключевые слова: фильтрация, моделирование, грунтовые воды, мультимедийные технологии, измерение качества, водо-проводимость.

Актуальность темы: В современных условиях при громадных масштабах гидротехнического мелиоративного, промышленного и других видов строительства, при неуклонном росте потребления минерально-сырьевых, водных и других природных ресурсов, в условиях интенсивного влияния различных сфер инженерной деятельности человека на природу и состояние ее ресурсов все более и более возрастают требования к эффективности и результативности гидрогеологических исследований, к качеству и достоверности получаемой при этом исходной информации, к надежности и обоснованности выполняемых на основе изысканий оценок, рекомендаций, проектных решений и инженерных прогнозов.

Целью исследований является разработка и научное обоснование компоновочно-конструктивных решений инженерной защиты грунтовых вод от загрязнений фильтратом накопителей промышленных отходов.

Настоящая цель потребовала решения следующих конкретных **задач исследования:**

- выполнить анализ современного состояния систем сооружений и устройств инженерной защиты и обобщить существующий опыт расчета распространения фильтрата из накопителей промышленных отходов;
- научно обосновать систему математических моделей прогнозирования параметров загрязнения грунтовых вод фильтратом из накопителей;
- разработать конструкции противофильтрационных элементов для накопителей промышленных отходов;
- провести экспериментальные натурные и лабораторные исследования по обоснованию элементов и систем компоновочно-конструктивных решений противофильтрационной и дренажной защиты;
- предложить методики фильтрационного расчета разработанных схем противофильтрационной защиты и оценки их эффективности;

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- разработать рекомендации по повышению эффективности инженерной защиты грунтовых вод от загрязнения фильтратом накопителей отходов в конкретных условиях их эксплуатации.

Объект исследования: Водоснабжение частных домов Самаркандской области из подземных источников. Установки очистки подземных вод.

Предмет исследования: Технология очистки подземных вод.

Методы исследования: При проведении работ, применялись аналитический, практический, статистический методы исследования, также анализировались нормативно-технические нормативы.

Научная новизна исследования заключается в следующем:

- ✓ обосновано теоретическое решение задачи по определению параметров загрязнения грунтовых вод фильтратом из накопителей промышленных отходов;
- ✓ получены экспериментальные зависимости по определению параметров зон и концентраций загрязнения грунтовых вод фильтратом из накопителей;
- ✓ теоретически и экспериментально обоснованы конструктивно - компоновочные схемы противofiltrационной и дренажной защиты при взаимодействии загрязненного фильтрата из накопителя с естественным грунтовым потоком;
- ✓ предложены усовершенствованные компоновочно-конструктивные схемы, противofiltrационные защиты, включающие комбинированные экраны повышенной надежности с кольматирующим и «самозалечивающим» слоями и, защищенные патентом на изобретение, фунтовые стенки с фильтрующе-сорбирующими элементами

Практическая значимость работы заключается в разработке рекомендаций по повышению эффективности инженерной защиты грунтовых вод от загрязнения фильтратом из накопителей промышленных отходов за счет применения усовершенствованных компоновочных схем и конструкций противofiltrационной и дренажной защиты.

С помощью моделирования решаются прямые, обратные и обобщенные задачи фильтрации подземных вод.

Решение прямых задач сводится к определению отдельных гидродинамических элементов потока (напоров, расходов, скоростей движения) при конкретных начальных и граничных условиях и параметрах потока, заданных на модели, как в естественных условиях, так и при учете воздействия инженерных сооружений. В большинстве своем эти задачи связаны с прогнозом условий фильтрации при проектировании конкретных объектов (прогнозы подпора в районах создания водохранилищ и подъема уровня грунтовых вод на массивах орошения, эффективности работы дренажных систем, водопонизительных установок и водозаборов подземных вод и т. п.) и в зависимости от сложности гидрогеологических условий они могут быть одномерными, двухмерными и значительно реже - пространственными.

Решение обратных задач заключается в определении и уточнении фильтрационных характеристик или граничных условий потоков по данным о распределении их напоров и расходов. Такие задачи обычно решаются подбором до получения приемлемого совпадения распределения напоров (или расходов) с наблюдаемыми в природных условиях. На практике, с помощью решения обратных задач определяют значения коэффициентов фильтрации, водоотдачи, пьезо- или уровнепроводности, оценивают величины инфильтрационного или глубинного питания, степень и характер гидравлической связи подземных и поверхностных вод и другие показатели.

Таким образом, решение обратных задач при моделировании используется как метод более полного освещения гидрогеологических особенностей изучаемого объекта и вместе с тем как метод оценки достоверности построенной модели, степени ее соответствия природной фильтрационной схеме и надежности выполняемых на ее основе инженерных прогнозов. Обоснование достоверности построенной модели включает:

1. определение и уточнение параметров фильтрационной среды, и обоснование их достоверности воспроизведением опытных откачек, эффекта действующих водозаборов и т. п.;
2. уточнение особенностей и строения фильтрационной схемы изучаемого объекта;
3. уточнение гидродинамической роли границ и действующих на них граничных условий;
4. определение элементов водного баланса или их уточнение;
5. построение фильтрационной модели и качественное обоснование ее достоверности;
6. количественную оценку точности и достоверности построенной модели и выполненных на ней прогнозов.

Обобщенные задачи решаются для получения общей характеристики какого-либо фильтрационного процесса или с использованием безразмерных параметров, или путем перебора всех возможных значений параметров, характерных для изучаемого процесса. Цель таких решений - получение графических или аналитических зависимостей на основе статистической обработки и обобщения полученных решений.

В зависимости от размеров изучаемого объекта, степени изученности и сложности его гидрогеологических условий, типа решаемых задач и стадии осуществления исследований моделирование подразделяется по степени детальности (по И. К. Гавич) на обзорное, выполняемое в масштабах мельче 1:500000, региональное — от 1:500000 до 1:50000 и детальное — крупнее 1:50000.

Обзорное моделирование применяется при региональном гидрогеологическом изучении территории страны в целях обоснования схем комплексного использования водных ресурсов, планирования водохозяйственных мероприятий, региональной оценки естественных и эксплуатационных ресурсов, изучения гидрогеологических особенностей артезианских бассейнов и других водонапорных систем.

Региональное моделирование используется при гидрогеологическом изучении отдельных крупных месторождений подземных вод, частей водонапорных систем, крупных инженерных сооружений и других объектов для оценки перспектив их промышленного освоения, определения эксплуатационных ресурсов, гидрогеологических характеристик и осуществления различных инженерных прогнозов. При детальном моделировании решаются самые разнообразные гидрогеологические задачи по изучению и геолого-промышленной оценке месторождений подземных вод или их участков, осуществлению прогнозов и обоснованию проектирования на различных стадиях гидрогеологических исследований.

Особую важность представляют данные о внешних и внутренних границах области фильтрации и действующих на них граничных условиях, а также о параметрах и строении изучаемого объекта. В связи с этим при проведении изысканий следует предусматривать комплекс работ по выявлению границ области фильтрации, изучению их характера и свойственных им граничных условий (рекогносцировочные обследования, геофизические и гидрологические работы, стационарные наблюдения, опытно-фильтрационные работы и др.).

На первоначальных стадиях изучения объекта исходный материал должен обеспечить изучение с помощью моделирования общих гидрогеологических условий, выявление и оценку

роли действующих факторов, и основные направления в проведении дальнейших исследований.

Заключение.

Получение перечисленных выше материалов возможно при широком использовании геофизических методов исследований, аэрофотосъемки, скоростных методов бурения и опробования скважин, например, применении экспресс-методов, выполнении мощных кустовых и групповых откачек, проведении в необходимых объемах гидрометрических, гидрологических, режимных и других работ.

Накопленный опыт использования моделирования в гидрогеологических исследованиях свидетельствует о том, что применение моделирования вносит определенные изменения и дополнения в методику их организации и проведения, которые следует учитывать при проектировании разведочных гидрогеологических работ:

- 1) применение моделирования планируется с учетом проекта гидрогеологических исследований, который должен содержать перечень намечаемых к решению моделированием задач с указанием возможных методов их решения и обоснования надежности выполняемых оценок и прогнозов;
- 2) намечаемые для использования при решении обратных задач опытно-фильтрационные работы и наблюдения следует проводить с учетом обеспечения ими исходной информации в достаточном количестве и соответствующем качестве;
- 3) при необходимости уточнения параметров, построения карт их распределения и обоснования достоверности модели проектом работ необходимо предусмотреть составление карт гидроизогипс и гидроизопьез по всем изучаемым и гидравлически связанным с ними водоносным горизонтам (при возможности на несколько моментов времени);
- 4) для установления характера границ области фильтрации и действующих на них граничных условий следует проводить комплекс дополнительных работ, обеспечивающих достоверное их определение и количественную оценку;
- 5) комплекс гидрогеологических и других исследований следует корректировать и выполнять в целях обеспечения успешного решения поставленных задач методом моделирования (достоверное обоснование фильтрационной схемы, однозначность решения обратных задач, надежность исходной информации). Только при правильной научно обоснованной его постановке, выполнении изложенных требований и творческом его применении моделирование может обеспечить надежное и эффективное решение поставленных гидрогеологических задач.

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О ПЕРСПЕКТИВЕ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОГО И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА МЕЖДУ УЗБЕКИСТАНом И ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИЕЙ

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Узбекистан и Великобритания имеют долгую историю политического, экономического и культурного сотрудничества, и недавние события только укрепили перспективы более тесного партнерства между двумя странами. В последние годы Великобритания проявляет растущий интерес к Узбекистану, признавая его потенциал в качестве ключевого игрока в Центральной Азии, в то время как Узбекистан добился значительного прогресса в таких областях, как права человека, демократия и экономическое развитие, что привело к более активному взаимодействию с международным сообществом.

Узбекистан, расположенный в Центральной Азии, является самой густонаселенной страной в регионе с богатым культурным наследием и растущей экономикой. Страна богата природными ресурсами, в том числе нефтью, газом, полезными ископаемыми и хлопком, а также большим, молодым и образованным населением. В последние годы Узбекистан добился значительного прогресса в политических и экономических реформах и становится все более важным игроком в регионе. Это привело к расширению взаимодействия с международным сообществом, включая Соединенное Королевство.

Великобритания имеет долгую торговую и дипломатическую историю с Узбекистаном и в последние годы проявляет растущий интерес к стране. Великобритания признает потенциал Узбекистана как ключевого игрока в Центральной Азии и стремится углубить отношения с этой страной. Великобритания была особенно активна в развитии экономических и торговых отношений, признавая богатые природные ресурсы страны и многочисленное, молодое и образованное население. Великобритания также активно выступает за права человека и демократию в Узбекистане и предоставляет техническую помощь и экспертные знания для поддержки реформ в этих областях.

Великобритания активно участвует в региональных форумах в Центральной Азии, таких как программа Центральноазиатского регионального экономического сотрудничества (ЦАРЭС), которая способствует региональной экономической интеграции и торговле. Это предоставило британским компаниям платформу для взаимодействия с Узбекистаном и другими странами Центральной Азии, а также для изучения новых торговых и инвестиционных возможностей. В последние годы Великобритания и Узбекистан подписали несколько соглашений для дальнейшего углубления своих торговых и инвестиционных отношений, в том числе Соглашение об избежании двойного налогообложения и Меморандум о взаимопонимании в области торговли и инвестиций.

В последние годы и Великобритания, и Узбекистан продемонстрировали твердую приверженность укреплению своего политического сотрудничества и предприняли конкретные шаги для углубления двусторонних отношений. В 2018 году Великобритания и Узбекистан создали Совместную межправительственную комиссию (JIGC) для содействия сотрудничеству по широкому кругу вопросов, включая торговлю, инвестиции, образование и культурный обмен. JIGC провел несколько встреч, результатом которых стали конкретные соглашения и инициативы по дальнейшему углублению отношений между двумя странами.

Одно из ключевых направлений сотрудничества между Великобританией и Узбекистаном находится в сфере образования. Великобритания является одним из ведущих мировых поставщиков высшего образования и является домом для некоторых из лучших университетов мира. Узбекистан признал важность образования и предпринял значительные шаги для повышения качества и доступности образования в стране. Великобритания и Узбекистан подписали несколько соглашений о сотрудничестве в области образования и обучения и разработали ряд совместных инициатив для продвижения программ обмена, сотрудничества в области исследований и наращивания потенциала.

В сфере безопасности и борьбы с терроризмом у Великобритании и Узбекистана также есть потенциал для сотрудничества. Узбекистан расположен на перекрестке Центральной Азии и Кавказа, и перед ним стоит задача устранения угроз безопасности в регионе, включая терроризм и экстремизм. Великобритания обладает богатым опытом в области безопасности и борьбы с терроризмом и активно участвует в международных усилиях по решению этих проблем. У Великобритании и Узбекистана есть потенциал для сотрудничества по инициативам в области безопасности и борьбы с терроризмом, таким как обмен информацией, наращивание потенциала и программы обучения.

В культурной сфере у Великобритании также есть много возможностей продемонстрировать свои сильные стороны и уникальность. Великобритания имеет богатое культурное наследие и является домом для некоторых из самых известных в мире музеев, галерей и культурных учреждений, таких как Британский музей, Национальная галерея, Тейт и Королевская шекспировская компания. В последние годы Великобритания также стала лидером в области современного искусства и дизайна, и многие молодые художники и дизайнеры сделали себе имя как дома, так и за рубежом.

Еще одна область потенциального сотрудничества – сельское хозяйство. Узбекистан является одним из крупнейших производителей хлопка, фруктов и овощей в регионе и имеет долгую историю сельскохозяйственного производства. Великобритания с ее сильным и диверсифицированным сельскохозяйственным сектором может предложить инвестиции и техническую поддержку, чтобы помочь Узбекистану расширить свое сельскохозяйственное производство, улучшить качество своей продукции и увеличить экспорт.

Великобритания также может поддержать усилия Узбекистана по развитию текстильной промышленности. В стране большой и растущий текстильный сектор, и у нее есть потенциал стать крупным игроком на мировом рынке текстиля. Великобритания, обладающая передовыми текстильными технологиями и опытом, может предложить инвестиции и техническую поддержку, чтобы помочь Узбекистану развивать свою текстильную промышленность и повышать качество и конкурентоспособность своей продукции.

В заключение следует отметить, что перспективы узбекско-британского политического сотрудничества являются позитивными и предлагают ряд возможностей для обеих стран. От содействия региональной стабильности и безопасности к поддержке экономического развития и политических реформ